

1 **Linking the core heat content to Earth's accretion**
2 **history**

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9 Abstract

10 The primordial heat content of the core and its initial composition are important param-
11 eters for the thermal and magnetic evolutions of the core, as well as for the physical and
12 chemical state of the core as it is today. In this study we use a parameterized model of
13 differentiation in a magma ocean setting, in which the magma ocean depth evolves dur-
14 ing accretion, to predict the composition of the primordial core. We couple this chem-
15 ical model to a thermal evolution model of the accreting metal to estimate the Earth's
16 core heat content at the end of its formation. We find that a range of differentiation sce-
17 narios, having different evolutions of the metal-silicates equilibration pressure and tem-
18 perature, can result in geochemically consistent models (*i.e.* having a mantle composi-
19 tion similar to the BSE). All these scenarios have in common two key features: (i) the
20 average pressure of metal-silicates equilibration is between 20 and 45 GPa (final pres-
21 sure between 40 and 60% of CMB pressure); (ii) 60 to 80% of Earth's mass is accreted
22 as reduced material with Si contents between 1.5 and 6 % wt of the core, and O contents
23 between 1 and 2 % wt. The chemical stratification is stable in most cases, though some
24 scenarios result in an unstable compositional stratification. Mixing an initially strati-
25 fied core requires a small fraction (between 1 and 10 %) of the energy released after a
26 giant impact. Importantly, our geochemically consistent scenarios each result in differ-
27 ent core temperatures, the temperature at the Core Mantle Boundary (CMB) after mix-
28 ing the core to an isentropic state ranging from 3925 to 4150 K. For example, scenar-
29 ios in which the magma ocean remains shallow for a large part of the accretion, and then
30 gets deeper at the end of accretion can produce chemically coherent models with cooler
31 cores. This suggests that independent constraints on the core temperature could in prin-
32 ciple be used as constraints for the differentiation conditions, and core composition. In
33 particular, we find that the abundance of light elements in the core correlates positively
34 with the temperature of the core at the end of accretion, as well as with the average pres-
35 sure of equilibration during differentiation.

36 1 Introduction

37 The physical and chemical properties of the early core are important for the ther-
38 mal and magnetic evolution of the core, as well as to understand the current properties
39 of the Earth's core such as core density deficit (Dziewonski & Anderson, 1981) or tem-

40 perature (Hirose et al., 2013; Labrosse, 2015). The initial conditions in temperature and
41 composition of the Earth’s core are important to understand how and when the inner
42 core started to crystallize and how it can trigger and sustain the Earth’s magnetic field
43 by itself (de Koker et al., 2012; Badro et al., 2018), or contribute to a thermally driven
44 dynamo (Andraut et al., 2016). The presence of light elements in the core has been at-
45 tested by the study of seismological data compared to pure iron equation of state (Birch,
46 1964) and it has an impact on the temperature profile of the Earth’s core, as there is a
47 compositional dependence of the liquidus temperature and latent heat release at the ICB
48 (Inner Core Boundary) (Labrosse, 2015).

49 The nature and concentrations of the light elements in the core have been explained
50 by metal/silicate partitioning experiments at high pressure. Those partitioning exper-
51 iments are designed to model the core/mantle segregation process in a magma ocean.
52 There is strong evidences that the core/mantle segregation process happened in a deep
53 magma ocean. Firstly, large impactors can release enough energy to melt the primor-
54 dial mantle almost completely, especially at the end of accretion (Tonks & Melosh, 1993;
55 Canup, 2004). Secondly, the timescale of core formation from Hf/W systematics indi-
56 cates a relatively rapid (between 30 and 100 Myrs) core segregation and high equilib-
57 rium efficiency (Kleine et al., 2009; Nimmo & Kleine, 2015), the latter being better ex-
58 plained by liquid-liquid segregation of metal and silicate (Rubie et al., 2003). Finally,
59 the siderophile elements abundances indicates that metal and silicate equilibrated deep
60 in the magma ocean (Drake & Richter, 2002; M. A. Bouhifd & Jephcoat, 2003), which
61 has implications for the nature and abundance of light elements in the core. The the-
62 ory of a deep magma ocean has lead to the creation of important models of Earth’s core
63 accretion and segregation based on the partitioning behavior of siderophile elements. Ni
64 and Co partitioning behaviour put constraints on the maximum extent of the magma
65 ocean (to a depth between 40 to 60 % of the CMB depth M. Bouhifd & Jephcoat, 2011;
66 Siebert et al., 2012), while the partitioning of the less siderophile elements (V,Cr, Mn,
67 Nb, Ta), for which partitioning behavior is more dependent on oxygen fugacity (Wood
68 et al., 2008; Tuff et al., 2011; Cartier, Hammouda, Doucelance, et al., 2014) showed that
69 the conditions of mantle/core segregation on the Earth became more oxidized (Wood et
70 al., 2008; Fischer et al., 2015; Rubie et al., 2015). These models also provide predictions
71 of light elements abundances accounting for the core density deficit, mostly Si and O (Tsuno
72 et al., 2013; Fischer et al., 2015) with an important contribution from S (Boujibar et al.,

73 2014; Laurenz et al., 2016). Some trace elements could also contribute to the core den-
74 sity deficit such as C (Chi et al., 2014; Dasgupta & Grewal, 2019), H (Clesi et al., 2018;
75 Malavergne et al., 2019) and N (Roskosz et al., 2013; Speelmanns et al., 2018).

76 Other elements may also have contributed to the onset of the geodynamo (such as
77 Mg, Badro et al., 2018), or to the heat budget and thermal evolution of the early core
78 (for instance U or K, M. A. Bouhifd et al., 2007; Faure et al., 2020). Putting constraints
79 on the energy budget of the core is important for understanding the thermal and mag-
80 netic evolution of the core, and constraining the age of the inner core (Nimmo, 2007; Sea-
81 gle et al., 2013; Labrosse, 2015).

82 The inner-core is much younger than the Earth’s (0.5 to 1.5 Gyrs, Labrosse, 2015),
83 and its crystallization has a significant impact on the geodynamo (Landeau et al., 2017).
84 Estimating the initial heat content and the heat fluxes at the CMB is then important
85 to explain the current thermal state of the core (Nimmo, 2007; Seagle et al., 2013; Labrosse,
86 2015; Andrault et al., 2016). The initial heat budget depend on the physical process of
87 core formation. A core formed by diapirism tend to be cooler, as the gravitational en-
88 ergy released during core formation is dissipated mostly in the silicates rather than in
89 the metal (Ke & Solomatov, 2009; Monteux et al., 2009).

90 On the other hand, a higher fraction of the gravitational energy would be released
91 in the metal if it separated from the silicates through channels (Ke & Solomatov, 2009)
92 or as an emulsion in a trail conduit (King & Olson, 2011; Fleck et al., 2018). The incor-
93 poration of heat producing element (Faure et al., 2020) into the core also has an influ-
94 ence on the initial heat content and its evolution through time (Seagle et al., 2013; Labrosse,
95 2015).

96 In this study, we aim at linking the chemical models that explains the core den-
97 sity deficit and the bulk silicate earth (BSE) composition through metal/silicate equi-
98 librium in a magma ocean (e.g. Fischer et al., 2015) and provide at the same time an
99 estimate of the Earth’s core heat content and temperature by using a thermal model to
100 calculate the evolution of the temperature of the metal while it sinks to form the core.
101 We use a model of continuous accretion where we parameterize the pressure and tem-
102 perature of metal/silicate equilibrium, and apply to the resulting metallic phase a ther-
103 mal evolution model through the solid mantle and core growth. At the end of the cal-
104 culation, we get a composition for a stratified core, a bulk composition for the mantle

105 and the initial heat content of the core that can be attributed to core formation, for mod-
 106 els that are chemically coherent with the Earth chondritic composition (McDonough &
 107 Sun, 1995; McDonough, 2003).

108 **2 Thermal evolution of the metal phase**

109 Our model follows the deep magma ocean conceptual model, according to which
 110 the Earth is covered by a magma ocean which depth evolves with time as accretion pro-
 111 ceeds. Each impact delivers a mass of metal δM_m , which is assumed to disperse in the
 112 magma ocean, accumulate at its base, and migrate through the solid part of the man-
 113 tle as a diapir of radius R_d .

114 We develop here an analytical model for the thermal evolution of the metal phase
 115 increment during its descent through the solid mantle toward the growing core, taking
 116 into account compression heating, viscous dissipation heating, and heat exchange with
 117 the surrounding silicates. The mass of the Earth is a fraction f of its final mass; the fi-
 118 nal thermal state of the core will be obtained by considering the full accretion history,
 119 each metal mass increment evolving according to the model described in this section. The
 120 parameters used in the model will be described in this section, and the list of paramete-
 121 r is given in Table 1.

122 The model involves three steps which are detailed below.

123 **2.1 Initial conditions**

124 We do not model heat transfer between metal and silicates within the magma ocean.
 125 Instead, we assume that the metal phase equilibrates thermally with the surrounding sil-
 126 icates, so that the pressure and temperature of the metal when it accumulates at the base
 127 of the magma ocean are equal to the pressure $P_{\text{eq}}(f)$ and temperature $T_{\text{eq}}(f)$ defining
 128 the lower boundary of the magma ocean. Since Hf-W systematics and siderophiles abun-
 129 dance in the BSE argue for significant metal-silicates chemical equilibration (Kleine et
 130 al., 2009), it seems reasonable to assume that the metal equilibrates thermally with the
 131 silicates at the base of the magma ocean.

Symbol	Parameter or variable	Value(s) and unit
P_{eq}	Pressure at the base of magma ocean	Pa or GPa
T_{eq}	Temperature at the base of magma ocean	K
f	Accreted mass fraction of the Earth	[0.05;1] no units
R_{\oplus}	Radius of the Earth	6370 km- 6.370 10 ⁶ m
$R_{\oplus}(f)$	Radius of the Earth at a given step of accretion	$R_{\oplus} \times f^{1/3}$
$R_{\text{CMB}}(f)$	Radius of the core at a given step of accretion	$3470 \times f^{1/3}$ km
G	Gravitational constant	$6.674 \times 10^{-11} \text{m}^3 \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$
K_d	Exchange partitioning coefficient (molar)	-
χ_i^p	Concentration of element i in phase p	- wt% or mol% (see text)
$c_{p,s}$	Specific heat of silicate	$500 \text{J} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$
$c_{p,m}$	Specific heat of metal	$1000 \text{J} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$
Pe	Peclet number	- no unit
γ	Grüneisen parameter	- (no unit)
ρ_p	Density of phase p	- $\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$
ρ_0	Density of metal at P=0	- $\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$
g	gravity field	- $\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$
R_d	Radius of metallic diapirs	- m
$K_{S,m}$	Isentropic bulk modulus of metal	- GPa
T_{sm}	Temperature of solid mantle	-K
ε	Fraction of dissipation energy going into the metal	- no unit
α_T	Thermal expansion coefficient of metal	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{K}^{-1}$
P_{center}	Final pressure at the centre of the Earth	360 GPa
α_{element}	expansion coefficient of an element	no unit
Q_{core}	Heat content of the core after accretion	- J
$T_{\text{CMB}}^{\text{is}}$	Temperature at CMB after mixing the core to an isentropic state	-K
$\delta^{BSE} \chi_i$	Relative variation of χ_i to the BSE	- %
μ_s	Viscosity of solid mantle	10^{18} Pa.s
D_s	Thermal diffusion coefficient of mantle	$10^{-6} \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$

Table 1. List of the symbols used in this study. When no value is given in the third column, the values are calculated in the model.

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2.2 Migration to the core

We now turn to describe the evolution of the metal phase while it migrates from the bottom of the magma ocean to the core, its pressure evolving in this process from $P_{\text{eq}}(f)$ to the core-mantle boundary pressure $P_{\text{CMB}}(f)$. Irrespectively of the mode of migration, the evolution of the temperature T of the metal is given by an equation of the form

$$C_{p,m} \frac{dT}{dt} = C_{p,m} \frac{\gamma T}{K_{S,m}} \frac{dP}{dt} - Q_{m \rightarrow s} + \Phi_m, \quad (1)$$

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where $C_{p,m}$ is the total heat capacity of the metal mass (*i.e.* $\delta M_m c_{p,m}$, where $c_{p,m}$ is the metal specific heat capacity), γ is the Gruneisen parameter, $K_{S,m}$ is the isentropic bulk modulus, $Q_{m \rightarrow s}$ is the heat flux from the metal to the surrounding silicates, and Φ_m is dissipative (*i.e.* viscous) heating in the metal phase. The first term on the right-hand side corresponds to compression heating.

Instead of solving Equation 1 to obtain T as a function of time, we transform it into an equation for T as a function of P , using the chain rule of derivation

$$\frac{d(\cdot)}{dt} = \frac{dz}{dt} \frac{dP}{dz} \frac{d(\cdot)}{dP} = v_d \rho_s g \frac{d(\cdot)}{dP}, \quad (2)$$

where v_d is the downward velocity of the metal phase. This allows to transform Equation 1 into the more convenient form

$$\frac{dT}{dP} = \frac{\gamma T}{K_{S,m}} - \frac{Q_{m \rightarrow s}}{C_{p,m} v_d \rho_s g} + \frac{\Phi_m}{C_{p,m} v_d \rho_s g}, \quad (3)$$

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which will be integrated from $P = P_{\text{eq}}(f)$ to the CMB pressure $P_{\text{CMB}}(f)$.

139

2.2.1 Compression heating

If metal to silicates heat transfer and dissipative heating are both neglected ($Q_{m \rightarrow s} = 0$ and $\Phi_m = 0$), then Equation 3 reduces to

$$\frac{dT}{dP} = \frac{\gamma T}{K_{S,m}} \quad (4)$$

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and the temperature of the metal phase simply follows an isentrope.

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2.2.2 Dissipative heating

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If the metal migrates with negligible inertia (*i.e.* if the flow around the diapir is a creeping flow, as expected given the high viscosity of the surrounding silicates), then

144 the total rate of energy dissipation is equal to the rate of change of gravitational energy
 145 E_p , which is approximately given by the product of mass anomaly $\frac{4\pi}{3}R_d^3\Delta\rho$, gravity g ,
 146 and rate of change of the height of the diapir center of mass (*i.e.* its velocity):

$$\frac{dE_p}{dt} \simeq \frac{4\pi}{3}R_d^3\Delta\rho g v_d. \quad (5)$$

147 with $\Delta\rho = \rho_m - \rho_s$ the difference between the density of metal and the surrounding
 148 silicate and R_d the radius of the metallic diapir. This is an approximate expression be-
 149 cause we do not take into account the modification of the gravity field associated with
 150 the displacement of the diapir mass. Of this, only a fraction is dissipated into heat in
 151 the metal, the remaining being released in the silicates or converted into strain energy.
 152 We denote by Φ_m and Φ_s the rate of dissipation in the metal and surrounding silicates,
 153 respectively, the rate of dissipative heating within the diapir being some fraction ϵ of the
 154 total rate of change of the potential energy, *i.e.* $\Phi_m = \epsilon \frac{dE_p}{dt}$. As shown below, the ra-
 155 tio Φ_m/Φ_s , and therefore ϵ , are likely small (Monteux et al., 2009; Samuel et al., 2010).

In the silicates surrounding the diapir, the velocity field v varies smoothly over a
 lengthscale $\sim R_d$ with an amplitude v_d (e.g. Batchelor, 1967, chapter 4.9). The dissi-
 pation rate per unit of volume, $\mu_s(\nabla v + \nabla v^T) : \nabla v$, is then be $\sim \mu_s v_d^2/R_d^2$, where μ_s
 is the dynamic viscosity of the silicates. The total dissipation rate in the silicates is

$$\Phi_s \sim R_d^3 \mu_s v_d^2 / R_d^2 \sim \mu_s R_d v_d^2. \quad (6)$$

In fact in the $\Phi_m \rightarrow 0$ limit in which the diapir velocity is given by the Stokes ve-
 locity for an inviscid sphere ($\mu_m = 0$ Pa.s)

$$v_d = \frac{\Delta\rho g R_d^2}{3\mu_s}, \quad (7)$$

156 the rate of dissipation is given by $4\pi\mu_s R_d v_d^2$, an expression which can be obtained either
 157 by substituting $\Delta\rho g R_d^2$ with $3\mu_s v_d$ (from Equation 7) in Equation 5, or by multiplying
 158 the Stokes drag force ($4\pi\mu_s R_d v_d$) with the velocity v_d . The diapir velocity would be some-
 159 what smaller than predicted by Equation 7 if the viscosity of the metal is taken into ac-
 160 count, but the effect is expected to be small because the velocity of the diapir is always
 161 controlled by the rate at which the surrounding silicates can deform (no more than a fac-
 162 tor of 2/3 in the unlikely limit of a diapir with $\eta_m \gg \eta_s$, according to the Stokes-Hadamard
 163 solution for a viscous sphere falling into a fluid with different viscosity (Batchelor, 1967,
 164 chapter 4.9). In the following, we will use Equation 7 when estimating the diapir veloc-
 165 ity.

166 Having obtained an order-of-magnitude expression for Φ_s , we now turn to estimat-
 167 ing the dissipation Φ_m in the diapir, assuming the flow within the diapir to be either lam-
 168 inar or turbulent.

If the flow within the diapir is laminar, then it will consist in a large scale axisym-
 metric vortex in which the velocity v varies over a length scale $\sim R_d$, with an ampli-
 tude v_d . Denoting by μ_m the viscosity of the metal, the dissipation rate per unit of vol-
 ume is then $\sim \mu_m v_d^2 / R_d^2$, and the total dissipation rate is $\sim R_d^3 \mu_m v_d^2 / R^2 \sim R_d \mu_m v_d^2$.
 Comparing dissipation in the silicates (Equation 6) and metal, we have

$$\frac{\Phi_m}{\Phi_s} \sim \frac{\mu_m}{\mu_s}, \quad (8)$$

169 which is very small: taking for example $\mu_s = 10^{15}$ Pa.s for the silicates (a fairly low es-
 170 timate taking into account the possibility of partial melting) and $\mu_m = 10^{-2}$ Pa.s (Kono
 171 et al., 2015) gives $\Phi_m / \Phi_s = 10^{-17}$.

If instead the flow withing the diapir is turbulent, then the rate of dissipation would
 scale as the rate of kinetic energy input, which scales as the kinetic energy of the diapir,
 $\frac{1}{2} \delta M_m v_d^2 \sim \rho_m R_d^3 v_d^2$, divided by the overturn time R_d / v_d (Tennekes & Lumley, 1972).
 This gives

$$\Phi_m \sim \rho_m R_d^2 v_d^3 \quad (9)$$

and, taking again $\Phi_s \sim \mu_s R_d v_d^2$ from Equation 6, we obtain

$$\frac{\Phi_m}{\Phi_s} \sim \frac{\rho_m}{\rho_s} Re_s, \quad (10)$$

where

$$Re_s = \rho_s \frac{R_d v_d}{\mu_s} \quad (11)$$

172 is the Reynolds number of the diapir, defined with the viscosity of the silicates. The value
 173 of Re_s depends on the size of the diapir and viscosity of the mantle, but is likely very
 174 small. Taking for example $\mu_s = 10^{18}$ Pa.s and $R_d = 100$ km gives $v_d = 7 \times 10^{-5} \text{m.s}^{-1} =$
 175 20 cm/hour , $Re_s = 3 \times 10^{-14}$ and $\Phi_m / \Phi_s \simeq 6 \times 10^{-14}$. Maximizing the value of Re_s
 176 by taking $\mu_s = 10^{16}$ Pa.s and $R_d = 1000$ km gives $Re_s \simeq 3 \times 10^{-7}$ and $\Phi_m / \Phi_s \simeq 6 \times$
 177 10^{-7} , which is still small, albeit not as much as in the laminar case. This therefore sug-
 178 gests that dissipative heating would in general have a negligible effect of the thermal evo-
 179 lution of the diapirs.

180

2.2.3 Metal to silicates heat transfer

The discussion in section 2.2.2 suggests that dissipation happens almost exclusively in the silicates if the metal migrates as a diapir. In this limit, the diapir velocity is well approximated by the Stokes velocity (Equation 7). The metal to silicates heat flux then depends on the Péclet number (comparing advective heat transfer to diffusive heat transfer)

$$Pe = \frac{v_d R_d}{\kappa_s} \quad (12)$$

as

$$Q_{m \rightarrow s} = a 4\pi R_d^2 k_s \frac{T - T_{sm}}{R_d} Pe^{1/2}, \quad (13)$$

181

where k_s and κ_s are the thermal conductivity and diffusivity of the silicates, $a \simeq 0.46$

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(Ulvrová et al., 2011), and T_{sm} is the temperature of the surrounding solid mantle. The

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effect of temperature dependent viscosity will not affect significantly these laws in the

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relevant limit of $Pe \gg 1$, because in this limit the influence of the diapir on the tem-

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perature of the surrounding silicates is limited to a very thin thermal boundary layer (Morris,

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1982; Ribe, 1983).

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2.2.4 Solution

As described in details in supplementary section S1, using the results of sections 2.2.2 and 2.2.3, one can write the equation governing the evolution of T (Equation 3)

as

$$\frac{dT}{dP} - A(P)T = B(P), \quad (14)$$

where the two accessory functions $A(P)$ and $B(P)$ are defined as

$$A(P) = \frac{\gamma}{K_{S,m}} - 3 \frac{\rho_s c_{p,s}}{\rho_m c_{p,m}} \frac{a P e^{-\frac{1}{2}}}{\rho_s g R_d}, \quad (15)$$

$$B(P) = 3 \frac{\rho_s c_{p,s}}{\rho_m c_{p,m}} \frac{a P e^{-\frac{1}{2}}}{\rho_s g R_d} T_{sm} + \varepsilon \frac{\Delta\rho}{\rho_s \rho_m c_{p,m}}. \quad (16)$$

The solution of this equation meeting the initial condition $T(P_{eq}) = T_{eq}$ is (Supplementary Information S1)

$$T(P) = \left[T_{eq} + \int_{P_{eq}}^P B(P') \exp\left(\int_{P_{eq}}^{P'} A(P'') dP''\right) dP' \right] \exp\left[-\int_{P_{eq}}^P A(P') dP'\right]. \quad (17)$$

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This expression, when applied at $P = P_{CMB}(f)$, allows to obtain the temperature of

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the metal phase when it reaches the core. Depending on the assumptions made on the

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pressure dependence of the metal and silicates properties, the integrals can be obtained

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analytically, or evaluated numerically.

192 **2.3 Further compression heating within the core**

193 Equation 17 gives the temperature of the metal when it reaches the core-mantle
 194 boundary. However, further growth of the Earth implies an additional pressure increase,
 195 with further compressional heating which has yet to be taken into account.

To estimate this effect, we assume that each metal addition stays at the same radius r in Earth's core, and has an initial pressure equal to the CMB pressure at the time at which it reached the core, *i.e.* $P(r = R_{\text{CMB}}(f)) = P_{\text{CMB}}(f)$. Indeed, each radius inside the core has been at some point in accretion the core radius as expressed in Table 1. Therefore, the initial pressure at these radii, before the core grew to its current size, was the pressure of the CMB after each step of accretion (the calculation of $P_{\text{CMB}}(f)$ is detailed in section 3). The final pressure profile $P(r)$ in the core is estimated from a second-order polynomial approximation of the PREM model (Dziewonski & Anderson, 1981) given by:

$$P(r) = P_{\text{center}} + \left(\frac{P_{\text{CMB}} - P_{\text{center}}}{R_{\text{CMB}}^2} \right) r^2, \quad (18)$$

196 where $P_{\text{center}} = 364$ GPa is the pressure at the center of the Earth, and $R_{\text{CMB}} = 3470$
 197 km is the final radius of the Earth's core and P_{CMB} is the pressure at the CMB at the
 198 end of the accretion.

We assume that there is no chemical or thermal mixing between each step of core growth, a model similar to Jacobson et al. (2017). We then assume that the metal follows an isentropic path, its temperature evolving according to

$$\frac{dT}{dP} = \frac{\gamma}{K_{S,m}} T. \quad (19)$$

199 Integrating Equation 19 from $P = P_{\text{CMB}}(f)$ to $P = P_{\text{core}}(r)$ gives a tempera-
 200 ture profile $T(r)$ which is usually not isentropic (because each diapir migrates to the core
 201 from different initial conditions) and can in principle be either stably or unstably strat-
 202 ified. We will then consider the possibility of having efficient radial mixing resulting in
 203 an isentropic core (see Section 5).

204 **3 Parameterization of core/mantle segregation**

205 The compositional constraints of our models come from previous accretion model
 206 obtained from metal/silicate high pressure partitioning of elements between metal and
 207 silicate (e.g. Siebert et al., 2012; Chi et al., 2014; Fischer et al., 2015; Clesi et al., 2016).

208 We base our model on the model of Fischer et al. (2015) from which we modify the pa-
 209 rameterization of the evolution of the pressure and temperature of metal/silicate equi-
 210 libration, and of the evolution of accreted material, as discussed in the following subsec-
 211 tions. In our model, as well as in Fischer et al. (2015), the Earth is accreted in 20 steps
 212 of accretion representing 5% of the Earth mass accreted. These steps represent the av-
 213 erage equilibrium created by impacts but are not to be mistaken for individual impacts.
 214 The step of accretion can be seen as the average equilibrium and compositional change
 215 of the core and mantle of a growing Earth, without having to model all impacts, which
 216 would require to model the entire accretion history as in Rubie et al. (2015). The pres-
 217 sure of equilibrium serves then as a proxy to the impact history: lower pressure at a given
 218 step means that for this step of accretion the impactors are smaller, while higher pres-
 219 sure at a given step of accretion means the impacts are bigger and more energetic (see
 220 for instance the scaling law of Nakajima et al., 2021). Further discussion on the why this
 221 method of continuous step accretion works in terms of bulk geochemistry can be found
 222 in the following references studying metal-silicate partitioning, among others: Wade and
 223 Wood (2005); Wood et al. (2008); Righter (2011); Tuff et al. (2011); M. Bouhifd and Jeph-
 224 coat (2011); Boujibar et al. (2014); Fischer et al. (2015); Badro et al. (2018); Grewal et
 225 al. (2019).

226 In the following sections, we test different accretion scenario by varying the pres-
 227 sure of equilibrium at each step, using a parameterized equation. The scenarios tested
 228 cover a large range of accretion history, for which we only keep the scenarios yielding man-
 229 tle composition close to the Bulk Silicate Earth.

230 **3.1 Parameterization of metal/silicates equilibration conditions**

231 ***3.1.1 Pressure and temperature of equilibration***

The first factor controlling chemical equilibrium between metal and silicate in a magma
 ocean is the pressure at the base of the magma ocean. We choose to parameterize the
 equilibration pressure P_{eq} using a modified cumulative Weibull distribution function writ-
 ten as:

$$P_{\text{eq}}(f) = a_P P_{\text{CMB}}(f) \frac{1 - e^{-(f/f_c)^\lambda}}{1 - e^{-(1/f_c)^\lambda}}, \quad (20)$$

232 where f is the mass fraction of Earth which has been accreted, $P_{\text{CMB}}(f)$ is the pressure
 233 at the core-mantle boundary (CMB), a_P a parameter setting the final equilibration pres-

Figure 1. Variation of P_{eq} , calculated by Equation 20, as a function of the Earth's mass fraction accreted (f) for: $a_P = 1$, $f_c = 0.5$ and varying λ values (left panel); $a_P = 1$, $\lambda = 5$ and varying f_c values (centre panel); $f_c = 0.5$, $\lambda = 5$ and varying a_P values (right panel).

234 sure, $P_{eq}(f = 1) = a_P P_{CMB}(f = 1)$; f_c and λ are the scale parameter (parameter
 235 defining both the moment in accretion when P_{eq} increase faster at high λ values and the
 236 transition from reduced to oxidized impactor) and shape parameter (parameter defin-
 237 ing the sharpness of the transition from shallow to deep magma ocean) of the Weibull
 238 distribution function $1 - e^{-(f/f_c)^\lambda}$. To simplify the compositional and thermal calcu-
 239 lation, we set the equilibration pressure at each step of accretion by calculating the CMB
 240 pressure assuming an hydrostatic gradient within the Earth, following equations (2.72)
 241 and (2.73) of Turcotte and Schubert (2002):

$$P_{CMB}(f) = \frac{4\pi}{3} \mathcal{G} \bar{\rho}_s(f) R_{CMB}(f)^2 \left[\frac{\bar{\rho}_s(f)}{2} \left(\frac{R_\oplus(f)^2}{R_{CMB}(f)^2} - 1 \right) + \Delta\bar{\rho} \left(1 - \frac{R_{CMB}(f)}{R_\oplus(f)} \right) \right], \quad (21)$$

242 where \mathcal{G} is the gravitational constant, and $R_\oplus(f)$ and $R_{CMB}(f)$ are the radii of the Earth
 243 and core, both functions of mass fraction accreted, given in Table 1. The mean densi-
 244 ties of silicate and metal at a given step of accretion ($\bar{\rho}_s(f)$ and $\Delta\bar{\rho} = \bar{\rho}_m(f) - \bar{\rho}_s(f)$)
 245 are obtained from the mass accreted, the mass fraction of metal (and therefore silicate)
 246 accreted and the radius of the Earth and of the core: $\bar{\rho}_s(f) = m_{silicate}^{accreted}(f)/V_{mantle}(f)$
 247 and $\bar{\rho}_m(f) = m_{metal}^{accreted}(f)/V_{core}(f)$. Note that the mean densities are not obtained by
 248 integration of a $P = f(\rho)$ relationship for metal or silicate, thus avoiding defining a spe-
 249 cific equation of state for the mantle.

250 The parameterization defined by Equation (20) allows to vary the shape of the equi-
 251 libration pressure curve $P_{eq}(f)$ as illustrated in Figure 1. With the shape parameter λ
 252 set to 0, Equation 20 reduces to $P_{eq}(f) = a_P P_{CMB}(f)$: the equilibration pressure is a

253 fixed ratio a_P of the CMB pressure, as assumed in many previous core formation mod-
 254 els (e.g. Wood et al., 2008; M. Bouhifd & Jephcoat, 2011; Fischer et al., 2015; Rubie et
 255 al., 2015; Clesi et al., 2016). If instead $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$, the Weibull cumulative distribution func-
 256 tion tends toward a step function equal to 0 for $f < f_c$ and 1 for $f > f_c$. In this limit,
 257 P_{eq} is equal to 0 for $f < f_c$ and $a_P P_{CMB}(f)$ for $f > f_c$. Choosing a finite value for λ
 258 allows to vary the shape of $P_{eq}(f)$ between these two limits, as shown in Figure 1: a mod-
 259 erate value of λ results in a gradual increase of $P_{eq}(f)$ (see the $\lambda \leq 3$ curves in the left
 260 panel of Figure 1), while a large value of λ results in an equilibration pressure starting
 261 low and increasing sharply around $f = f_c$, before approaching the $a_P P_{CMB}(f)$ curve
 262 (see the $\lambda = 5$ curves of Figure 1).

It will be convenient to discuss the results of the calculations in terms of the av-
 erage equilibration pressure $\overline{P_{eq}}$, defined as

$$\overline{P_{eq}} = a_P \int_0^1 P_{CMB}(f) \frac{1 - e^{-(f/f_c)^\lambda}}{1 - e^{-(1/f_c)^\lambda}} df. \quad (22)$$

263 For a given pair (f_c, λ) (i.e. the pair of parameter defining both the moment in accre-
 264 tion when P_{eq} increase faster at high λ values and the transition from reduced to oxi-
 265 dized impactor and the parameter defining the sharpness of the transition from shallow
 266 to deep magma ocean), there is a one-to-one relation between a_P and $\overline{P_{eq}}$. The evolu-
 267 tion of $P_{eq}(f)$ is therefore fully characterized by the $(\overline{P_{eq}}, f_c, \lambda)$ triplet, which can be used
 268 in place of the (a_P, f_c, λ) triplet.

The second factor controlling the equilibrium is the temperature of equilibrium be-
 tween metal and silicate and metal at the base of the magma ocean. We assume that
 the temperature of equilibrium is given by the liquidus temperature of the silicate from
 Andraut et al. (2011),

$$T_{eq} = 1940 \left(\frac{P_{eq}}{29} + 1 \right)^{1/1.9}, \quad (23)$$

269 which is higher than the liquidus of metal. Here P_{eq} is expressed in GPa, and T_{eq} in K.

270 **3.1.2 Physical meaning of P_{eq} and T_{eq}**

271 Following the chemical approach to mantle/core segregation, we do not go to the
 272 trouble of modeling each accretion impact. We use Equations 20 and 23 to parameter-
 273 ize the evolution of the equilibration conditions. As classically done in metal/silicate par-
 274 titioning studies, the growth of the planet and the change in composition is discretized

275 in several steps of accretion, with different step sizes corresponding to different percent-
 276 age of mass added to the planet (a non exhaustive list of this kind of model can be found
 277 in the following list, sampling different step size or approaches Wade & Wood, 2005; Wood
 278 et al., 2008; M. Bouhifd & Jephcoat, 2011; Boujibar et al., 2014; Fischer et al., 2015; Clesi
 279 et al., 2016; Suer et al., 2021). Each step represent the average of several impacts. If the
 280 impacts during one step are bigger and more energetic, then it will produce a deeper magma
 281 ocean, and therefore a higher value for P_{eq} (Tonks & Melosh, 1993; Nakajima et al., 2021).
 282 On the other hand, smaller, less energetic impacts will tend to result in a shallower magma
 283 ocean and lower values of P_{eq} . In all previous study, the accretion history is fixed prior
 284 to the calculation, while in our study we can test different accretion history by varying
 285 the depth of the magma ocean.

286 Figure 1 should then be read as a proxy of the impact history, through the evolu-
 287 tion of the magma ocean. We also combine the shape parameter with the compositional
 288 shift from reduced to oxidized accretion. The justification of this shift in composition
 289 is given in Section 3.2. The main motivation for combining the shape parameter f_c (pa-
 290 rameter defining the moment in accretion when P_{eq} increase faster at high λ values) in
 291 Equation 20 with the composition shift is to allow the model to be fully parameterized
 292 by three parameters instead of having four parameters to vary (which would multiply
 293 the number of simulation by 20). It also makes sense to use this parameter, since the in-
 294 crease in P_{eq} happens for $f > f_c$ at high values of λ , and is a proxy for larger impact
 295 of more evolved, more oxidized planetary embryos impacting at the end of accretion (Raymond
 296 et al., 2009; Rubie et al., 2015; Suer et al., 2021).

297 In Table 2, we list a summary of the physical and chemical meaning of the param-
 298 eters used in Equation 20. In Section 3.2, we will explain why we chose f_c to define a
 299 shift between reduced and accreted material. This model will span a lot of different sce-
 300 narios. There is some (a_P, f_c, λ) triplet values that can be directly translated into an easy
 301 understandable impact history:

- 302 • Very shallow magma ocean (low size impacts) accretion followed by giant impacts
 303 in the last 10% of accretion melting the entire mantle: $a_P = 1$, $f_c \sim 0.85 - 0.9$
 304 and $\lambda \sim 5$

Parameter values			Magma ocean evolution	Impactor history	Main impactor composition
$a_P \sim 0.05$	$f_c \sim 0.05$	$\lambda \sim 0$	shallow magma ocean, smooth increase	small impacts only	Oxidized
$a_P \sim 0.05$	$f_c \sim 0.05$	$\lambda \sim 5$	shallow magma ocean, sharp increase at the end	small impacts, a bit bigger at the end	Oxidized
$a_P \sim 0.05$	$f_c \sim 1$	$\lambda \sim 0$	shallow magma ocean, smooth increase	small impacts only	Reduced
$a_P \sim 0.05$	$f_c \sim 1$	$\lambda \sim 5$	shallow magma ocean, sharp increase at the end	small impacts, a bit bigger at the end	Reduced
$a_P \sim 1$	$f_c \sim 0.05$	$\lambda \sim 0$	deep magma ocean, smooth increase	medium size impact all along	Oxidized
$a_P \sim 1$	$f_c \sim 0.05$	$\lambda \sim 5$	shallow first, sharp transition to deep at the beginning	small first, get larger early in the accretion history	Oxidized
$a_P \sim 1$	$f_c \sim 1$	$\lambda \sim 0$	deep magma ocean, smooth increase	large impactors	Reduced
$a_P \sim 1$	$f_c \sim 1$	$\lambda \sim 5$	shallow first, sharp transition to deep toward the end	small first, large at the end	Reduced

Table 2. Physical and chemical meaning of the main combination of the parameters controlling Equation 20. This is a qualitative description, assuming the size of impactors controls the magma ocean depth. The effect described can be seen also in Figure 1.

- 305 • Small step accretion, followed by intermediate size impactors finalized by the Moon
306 forming impact melting more than 75% of the mantle (Suer et al., 2021): $a_P >$
307 0.75 , $f_c \sim 0.8$, $\lambda \sim 5$
- 308 • The original Fischer et al. (2015) model on which this study is based: $a_P \sim 0.5$ –
309 0.75 , $f_c = 0.75$, $\lambda = 0$
- 310 • Steady increase of the magma ocean depth at 50% of P_{CMB} with accretion (Boujibar
311 et al., 2014; Clesi et al., 2016): $a_P \sim 0.5$, $f_c = 0.6 - 1$, $\lambda = 0$
- 312 • Oxidized history of accretion (Siebert et al., 2013): $a_P \sim 0.4 - 0.5$, $f_c \rightarrow 0.05$,
313 $\lambda = 0$

314 A Moon forming impact effect with some metal-silicate equilibrium is modeled by the
315 last 10% of accretion for high values of λ , f_c and a_P . An error is introduced by the fact
316 that we extract metal in 2 steps instead of modeling one final impact corresponding to
317 10% of the Earth’s mass.

318 In terms of chemical compositions and for the elements we chose to study, the er-
319 ror introduced by the model is not important, as the main control of the model is the
320 concentration of Ni and Co (Fischer et al., 2015), which are not that much affected by
321 the Moon-forming impact if there is some equilibrium between metal and silicate (Clesi
322 et al., 2020). The error introduced for the temperature is also low, since most of the core
323 has already acquired its heat. However, this model cannot account for core-merging events
324 during late accretion, because by construction it needs to have some chemical equilib-
325 rium at some point.

326 **3.2 Composition of accreted material**

327 Following Fischer et al. (2015), we assume that the accreted material changes from
328 reduced to oxidized at a given time in accretion. This transition from reduced to oxi-
329 dized material is necessary to explain the partitioning behavior of moderately siderophile
330 elements which depend highly on oxygen fugacity such as Nb, Ta, Cr and V (e.g. Tuff
331 et al., 2011; Cartier, Hammouda, Doucelance, et al., 2014), as well as the sulfur behav-
332 ior (Boujibar et al., 2014; Laurenz et al., 2016). It is also more coherent with dynam-
333 ical accretion model and distribution of oxidized material within the early solar system (Morbidelli
334 et al., 2000; Raymond et al., 2009; Raymond & Izidoro, 2017; Izidoro et al., 2021). While
335 in Fischer et al. (2015)’s model this change is assumed to occur when 75% of Earth’s mass

336 has been accreted, we here vary this time from a calculation to the other, assuming it
 337 happens at the accreted fraction f_c defined in the parameterization of the equilibration
 338 pressure (Equation (20)). The composition of the accreting material is derived from CI
 339 chondrites composition (Wasson & Kallemeyn, 1988) equilibrated for different oxygen
 340 fugacity, thus ensuring that refractory lithophile element concentrations will be close to
 341 the chondritic trend (for a full explanation of this choice, see Fischer et al. (2015) and
 342 references therein). The composition of accreting impactors is given in Table 3.

343 **3.3 Compositional model**

344 *3.3.1 Calculation of equilibrium compositions*

The equilibrium is set by reaction of an oxide $MO_{n/2}$ in the magma ocean trans-
 forming into a metal M in the metallic phase. This reaction is written:

where $MO_{n/2}^{m.o.}$ is the oxide in the silicate liquid (magma ocean) and M^m is the same el-
 element in its metallic form in the liquid metal alloy. The equilibrium constant of this re-
 action defines the exchange partitioning coefficient for element M, K_d^M . By combining
 Equations 20 and 23 it is possible to calculate the partitioning behavior between the liq-
 uid metal and the liquid silicate of moderately siderophile elements using the exchange
 partitioning coefficient K_d^M of element M (Ni, Co, Si, V, Cr or O), using the parametriza-
 tion

$$\log_{10}K_d^M = a_M + \frac{b_M}{T_{eq}} + \frac{c_M P_{eq}}{T_{eq}}, \quad (25)$$

where P_{eq} is expressed in GPa, T_{eq} in K. We use values of a_M , b_M and c_M obtained ex-
 perimentally by Fischer et al. (2015). The exchange partitioning coefficient for an ele-
 ment M of valence n is given by:

$$K_d^M = \frac{\chi_M^m}{\chi_{MO_{n/2}}^{m.o.}} \left(\frac{\chi_{FeO}^{m.o.}}{\chi_{Fe}^m} \right)^{n/2}. \quad (26)$$

345 where χ_M^m is the molar fraction of element M in the liquid metal, and $\chi_{MO_{n/2}}^{m.o.}$ is the mo-
 346 lar fraction of the corresponding oxide in the silicate liquid. At each impact the mass
 347 of silicate and metal accreted are equilibrated with each other at a pressure and tem-
 348 perature defined by Equations 20 and 23, which yields the partitioning behavior of mod-
 349 erately siderophile elements (Equation 25) at a given step of accretion and for given val-
 350 ues of a_P , f_c (parameter defining both the moment in accretion when P_{eq} increase faster

Elements	Reduced material	Oxidized material
Silicate phase		
SiO ₂	51.41	42.19
MgO	37.5	29.40
Al ₂ O ₃	4.62	3.63
CaO	3.75	2.95
FeO	2.24	21.13
NiO (ppm)	10.1	174
CoO (ppm)	5.1	83
Cr ₂ O ₃ (ppm)	4500	6170
V ₂ O ₃ (ppm)	203	164
Metallic phase		
Fe	91.1	89.07
Ni	5.55	10.0
Co	0.26	0.34
Si	2.4	0.0205
Cr (ppm)	6100	870
V (ppm)	9.24	0.775
O	0.04	0.4
Metallic mass fraction of the impactor		
-	0.313	0.165

Table 3. Impactor composition given in Fischer et al. (2015) supplementary material and used in our model. All units are in wt % except where ppm is specified.

351 at high λ values and the transition from reduced to oxidized impactor) and λ (param-
 352 eter defining the sharpness of the transition from shallow to deep magma ocean). The
 353 composition of the metallic phase accreted to the core is set by mass balance equations
 354 and partitioning behavior. The mass balance is derived from the technique described in
 355 the supplementary materials of Rubie et al. (2011), with a few modifications. The de-
 356 tail of the calculation is given in the Supplementary Information S2.

357 **3.3.2 Final compositions**

358 After each impact, we obtain the composition of the masses of metal and silicate
 359 that are added to the core and the mantle respectively. These compositions are not rep-
 360 resentative of the bulk evolution of the core and mantle, the latter being set by the cu-
 361 mulative effects of all the impacts. The composition and temperature of the metal added
 362 to the core evolves as accretion proceeds, as a result of the evolution of the equilibra-
 363 tion conditions and composition of the mantle. This implies that the core could end up
 364 being chemically and thermally stratified. This stratification is likely stable, since the
 365 equilibration conditions are likely to evolve toward higher temperature and pressure as
 366 the size of the planet increases, which helps incorporating light elements such as O and
 367 Si. Some degree of radial mixing may happen however, either when the metal is added
 368 the core (Landeau et al., 2016), or because of the possibly intense stirring induced by
 369 giant impacts (Jacobson et al., 2017). In what follows, we will consider two end-member
 370 scenarios assuming either no mixing, resulting in a compositionally and thermally strat-
 371 ified core, or perfect mixing, resulting in a homogeneous and isentropic core.

372 In the following, we will be dealing with the bulk composition of the mantle only,
 373 neglecting any heterogeneities in the mantle. On the other hand, we will refer to both
 374 stratified core concentrations and bulk core concentrations, which will be indicated by
 375 the super script *strati* or *bulk* respectively.

The discrimination of the results is made by comparing the final bulk mantle com-
 position of the model to the Bulk Silicate Earth (BSE) composition given in McDonough
 and Sun (1995). To calculate the final bulk composition we use an iterative approach,
 evolving the silicates composition according to

$$\chi_{i,\text{bulk}}^{s+}(f) = \frac{\chi_i^s(f)m_{\text{accreted}}^s(f) + \chi_{i,\text{bulk}}^{s-}M_{\text{mantle}}^-}{M_{\text{mantle}}^+} \quad (27)$$

376 where $\chi_{i,\text{bulk}}^{s-}(f)$ and $\chi_{i,\text{bulk}}^{s+}(f)$ are the bulk concentrations before and after the impact,
 377 and M_{mantle}^- and M_{mantle}^+ the masses of the mantle before and after the impact ($M_{\text{mantle}}^+ =$
 378 $M_{\text{mantle}}^- + m_{\text{accreted}}^s(f)$). With Equation 27, we obtain $\chi_{i,\text{bulk}}^s(f = 1)$ which is the BSE
 379 concentration for a given element. The same equation can be used with $m_{\text{accreted}}^m(f)$ and
 380 $M_{\text{core}}(f - 1)$ to calculate the bulk composition of the core.

381 4 Simplifying hypothesis for the temperature profile calculation

382 The metallic alloy is initially set at the same temperature as the silicate at the bot-
 383 tom of the magma ocean, where it acquire its composition. This temperature is given
 384 by Equation 23, and is straightforward to calculate as it depends only on the equilib-
 385 rium pressure set by Equation 20. Then the metal forms a diapir and goes through the
 386 solid mantle to reach the CMB and form the core, following Equation 17. Finally, the
 387 metal forming the core undergoes an isentropic compression as the core grows, follow-
 388 ing Equation 19. To solve EquationS 17 and 19 we need some simplifying hypothesis that
 389 are presented in this section. The choices made in this section are discussed in detail in
 390 Section 7.1.

391 4.1 Equation of state of liquid metal

392 The choice of an equation of state (EOS) for the metal is key here. The EOS has
 393 to be realistic, taking into account the effect of pressure and composition, while math-
 394 ematically simple enough to obtain closed form solutions of equations 17 and 19. Our
 395 strategy is to first obtain an EOS for pure iron, and then add a correction accounting
 396 for the effect of composition. Our EOS has to describe accurately the evolution of the
 397 density along a constant entropy compression path, since deviations from this path dur-
 398 ing the migration of a diapir are expected to be small (as argued in section 2.2.2). The
 399 target property is therefore $K_{S,m}(P)$. To constrain the EOS, we use the present-day den-
 400 sity profile in the core according to the PREM model, as well as experimental and *ab*
 401 *initio* estimates of the density of pure iron and iron alloys at various pressures and tem-
 402 peratures. One advantage of using PREM as a constraint is that we can reasonably as-
 403 sume that the core is close to isentropic and chemically homogeneous, which implies that
 404 the evolution of density with pressure in the core is a good measure of isentropic com-
 405 pression. Since in addition K_S is usually a weak function of temperature (Ichikawa et
 406 al., 2014; Kuwayama et al., 2020), the pressure dependence obtained from PREM should

Figure 2. Different equations of state for liquid metal and experimental and ab initio data. On the left, data covering the whole P-space relevant for Earth formation. On the right, close-up on the core conditions. The color scale indicate the temperature of experimental (Morard et al., 2013; Kuwayama et al., 2020) and ab initio data (Umemoto et al., 2014; Ichikawa et al., 2014), the white symbols are 300 K data points of Anderson and Ahrens (1994) and Zhang et al. (2018)). PREM model and its variations are the black lines (PREM for iron: solid, 7.5%wt density deficit: dashed line, 8.5%wt density deficit: dotted line, 9.5%wt density deficit: dotted-dashed line). The red line is a fit of the Murnaghan equation of state used for this study.

407 be rather robust. In contrast, the (P, T) conditions of individual experiments and cal-
 408 culations, when taken collectively, do not follow isentropic compression paths, which makes
 409 difficult to extract a parametrization for $K_{S,m}(P)$. Earth’s core is not made of pure iron,
 410 however, and the density profile from PREM therefore has to be corrected for the pres-
 411 ence of light elements. Figure 2 shows the data used to constrain the EOS, which include
 412 PREM’s density profile and experimental and *ab initio* estimates for various composi-
 413 tions. In order to highlight the effect of pressure, we normalize the density $\rho(P)$ of each
 414 data point by the density ρ_0 at low pressure and same composition. The density from
 415 PREM is corrected by assuming that the core is 7.5%, 8.5%, or 9.5% less dense than pure
 416 iron, to account for the presence of light elements.

We have tried several parametrisations for our EOS, and found that a simple Mur-
 naghan equation of state (Murnaghan, 1944) allows to match satisfactorily the composition-
 corrected density profile from PREM (density deficit of 8.5%) and the experimental and
ab initio data. The Murnaghan equation of state assumes that the isentropic bulk mod-
 ulus is a linear function of P ,

$$K_{S,m} = K_0 + K'P, \quad (28)$$

where K_0 is the bulk modulus at zero pressure and K' its derivative with respect to pres-
 sure. Integration of the relation $K_{S,m} = \rho \frac{\partial P}{\partial \rho}$ over ρ yields

$$\frac{\rho_m(P)}{\rho_0} = \left(1 + \frac{K'}{K_0}P\right)^{1/K'}. \quad (29)$$

Assuming that the core is 8.5% less dense than pure iron, we find that the Murnaghan
 equation adequately describes the corrected PREM profile and lower pressure data with
 $K_0 = 128.49$ GPa and $K' = 3.67$ (red curve on Figure 2). In our model, the metal is
 a Fe-Ni-Co-Si-O-V-Cr alloy, and the effect of composition on ρ_0 is obtained as follows:

$$\rho_0 = (\chi_{Fe}^m \rho_0^{Fe} + \chi_{Ni}^m \rho_0^{Ni} + \chi_{Co}^m \rho_0^{Co} + \chi_V^m \rho_0^V + \chi_{Cr}^m \rho_0^{Cr}) \exp(\alpha_{Si} \chi_{Si}^m + \alpha_O \chi_O^m), \quad (30)$$

417 where $\alpha_{Si} = -0.91$ and $\alpha_O = -1.8$ are the expansion coefficient of Si and O in metal-
 418 lic alloys. The values ρ_0^i are given in Table 4.1. Equation 30 is calculated assuming the
 419 transition metals (Ni, Co, V and Cr) are replacing Fe atoms in the alloy, and therefore
 420 change the mass without changing the volume. For non-metallic elements (Si and O),
 421 the volume and the mass are changed, as shown by Alfè et al. (2002), therefore their ef-
 422 fect on density has to be taken into account through the expansion coefficient (the ex-
 423 ponential factor in Equation 30). The full demonstration of the formula is given in Ap-
 424 pendix A of Deguen and Cardin (2011). By including Equation 30 into Equation 29, we

ρ_0^{Fe}	ρ_0^{Ni}	ρ_0^{Co}	ρ_0^V	ρ_0^{Cr}	α_{Si}	α_O
7019	7900	8900	6100	7190	-0.91	-1.8

Table 4. Values of ρ_0^i in kg.m^{-3} and expansion coefficient for light elements (Si and O) used in equation 30. The expansion coefficient are taken from Deguen and Cardin (2011) and references therein. Iron value is from (Anderson & Ahrens, 1994) while the other element are from thermodynamic tables

425 get an equation of state that take into account pressure dependency (through Equation
426 29) and compositionnal dependency (through Equation 30).

4.2 Compression-driven heating

We first consider the case where $Pe \rightarrow \infty$ and $\varepsilon = 0$. This means that the diffusion of temperature between the metal and the surrounding mantle is negligible and that the gravitational energy dissipation happens in the mantle only. In these conditions, $A(P) = -\frac{\gamma}{K_{S,m}}$, $B(P) = 0$, and Equation 17 simplifies to Equation 19. To solve this equation we need the evolution of the Grüneisen parameter with pressure. We use the equation of Al'Tshuler et al. (1987):

$$\gamma(P) = \gamma_\infty + (\gamma_0 - \gamma_\infty) \left(\frac{\rho_0}{\rho_m} \right)^\beta, \quad (31)$$

with $\gamma_\infty = 1.305$, $\gamma_0 = 1.875$ and $\beta = \gamma_0/(\gamma_0 - \gamma_\infty)$ (values from Dewaele et al., 2006). When combining Equations 31 and 28 in Equation 19, it is possible to integrate the equation and have an analytical solution given by

$$T(P) = T_{\text{eq}} \left(\frac{\rho_m(P)}{\rho_m(P_{\text{eq}})} \right)^{\gamma_\infty} \exp \left[\frac{\gamma_0 - \gamma_\infty}{\beta} \left(\left(\frac{\rho_0}{\rho_m(P_{\text{eq}})} \right)^\beta - \left(\frac{\rho_0}{\rho_m(P)} \right)^\beta \right) \right], \quad (32)$$

428 where $P(r)$ is the final pressure in the core at radius r (Equation 18). The ratio $\frac{\rho_0}{\rho_m}$ is
429 given by Equation 29.

4.3 Dissipation of gravitational energy

431 In the previous section, both dissipation and diffusion terms were set to zero. Here
432 we still assume that $Pe \rightarrow \infty$, but now examine the case where some fraction ϵ of dis-
433 sipative heating does heat the metal. While ε is likely very small if the metal migrates

434 as a diapir (section 2.2.2), it may not be so if the metal migrates by percolating through
 435 the mantle.

436 We do not calculate directly the dissipation, but rather test several fixed values of
 437 ε between 0 and 1. In this case, Equation 17, using Equation 31, becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
 T(P_{\text{CMB}}(f)) = & \left(\frac{\rho_m(P_{\text{CMB}})}{\rho_m(P_{\text{eq}})} \right)^{\gamma_\infty} \exp \left[\frac{\gamma_0 - \gamma_\infty}{\beta} \left(\left(\frac{\rho_0}{\rho_m(P_{\text{eq}})} \right)^\beta - \left(\frac{\rho_0}{\rho_m(P_{\text{CMB}})} \right)^\beta \right) \right] \times \\
 & \left[T_{\text{eq}} + \varepsilon C_{p,m} \int_{P_{\text{eq}}}^{P_{\text{CMB}}} \left(\frac{1}{\rho_s} - \frac{1}{\rho_m(P')} \right) \left(\frac{\rho_m(P')}{\rho_m(P_{\text{eq}})} \right)^{\gamma_\infty} \times \right. \\
 & \left. \exp \left\{ \frac{\gamma_0 - \gamma_\infty}{\beta} \left(\left(\frac{\rho_0}{\rho_m(P_{\text{eq}})} \right)^\beta - \left(\frac{\rho_0}{\rho_m(P')} \right)^\beta \right) \right\} dP' \right], \quad (33)
 \end{aligned}$$

438 which is solved numerically, with $\rho_s(f)$ being calculated at each accretion step in the same
 439 way as in Equation 21.

440 5 Core heat content and CMB temperature

441 5.1 Calculation of heat content and isentropic temperature

442 Once the core temperature and density profiles at the end of accretion have been
 443 obtained, we calculate the heat content of the core (Q_{core}) right after the accretion as

$$Q_{\text{core}} = \iiint \rho_m c_{p,m} T dV. \quad (34)$$

From this we estimate the isentropic temperature profile corresponding to the same
 heat content, assuming that the core has been thoroughly mixed, possibly as a result of
 mechanical stirring associated with planetary impacts or convection. This results in a
 chemically homogeneous (rather than chemically stratified) core, with composition ob-
 tained from Equation 27. $\rho_m(r)$ is then recalculated using Equation 29 and the final core
 pressure given by Equation 18. The isentropic profile is calculated from

$$\left(\frac{\partial \ln T}{\partial \ln \rho_m} \right)_s = \gamma, \quad (35)$$

which gives

$$T^{\text{is}}(r) = T_{\text{CMB}}^{\text{is}} \left(\frac{\rho_m(r)}{\rho_{\text{CMB}}} \right)^{\gamma_\infty} \exp \left[\frac{\gamma_0 - \gamma_\infty}{\beta} \left(\left(\frac{\rho_0}{\rho_{\text{CMB}}} \right)^\beta - \left(\frac{\rho_0}{\rho_m(r)} \right)^\beta \right) \right]. \quad (36)$$

The key parameter to be determined is the CMB temperature ($T_{\text{CMB}}^{\text{is}}$). Combining Equation 34 and Equation 36 gives

$$T_{\text{CMB}}^{\text{is}} = \frac{Q_{\text{core}}}{4\pi\rho_{\text{CMB}}c_{p,m}} \left[\int_0^{R_{\text{CMB}}} \left(\frac{\rho_m(r)}{\rho_{\text{CMB}}} \right)^{\gamma_\infty+1} \exp \left(\frac{\gamma_0 - \gamma_\infty}{\beta} \left(\left(\frac{\rho_0}{\rho_{\text{CMB}}} \right)^\beta - \left(\frac{\rho_0}{\rho_m(r)} \right)^\beta \right) \right) r^2 dr \right]^{-1}, \quad (37)$$

444 which is evaluated numerically. In this equation, ρ_{CMB} is the density of the core at the
 445 CMB, determined after isentropic mixing by Equation 29.

446 Perfect mixing of the core is clearly not guaranteed, but the CMB temperature ob-
 447 tained through the procedure described above is at least a convenient measure of the ther-
 448 mal state of the core at the end of core formation.

449 5.2 Effect of the accretion parameters on the core thermal state

450 We now discuss the effect of the parameters a_P , λ (parameter defining the sharp-
 451 ness of the transition from shallow to deep magma ocean), and f_c (parameter defining
 452 both the moment in accretion when P_{eq} increase faster at high λ values and the tran-
 453 sition from reduced to oxidized impactor) of the equilibration pressure parametrization
 454 on the post-mixing temperature of the core. As an example, we discuss a simple model
 455 in which the composition of the metal added to the core changes at $f = f_c$, from pure
 456 iron with $\rho_0 = 7019 \text{ kg.m}^{-3}$ (Anderson & Ahrens, 1994) for $f < f_c$ to an iron alloy
 457 with $\rho_0 = 6318 \text{ kg.m}^{-3}$ (10% lighter than pure iron) for the second part of accretion
 458 ($f > f_c$). As a reminder, the effect of these parameters on the evolution of the equi-
 459 libration pressure as a function of f are shown in Figure 1.

460 Figure 3 illustrates the three steps of our model:

461 (i) The first column shows the evolution of the P, T conditions of the metal phase
 462 while it migrates from the base of the magma ocean to the CMB at time of each core-
 463 forming event. We assume here negligible heat transfer between the metal and surround-
 464 ing mantle, and no dissipative heating of the metal.

465 On the different panels are shown the silicates liquidus (black line, Equation 23),
 466 which gives the P, T conditions from which each metal addition starts its migration through
 467 the mantle.

468 The orange arrows show the paths of individual metal masses migrating as diapirs
 469 from two different pressures, corresponding to different magma ocean depths (blue cir-

Figure 3. Summary of the different steps of the calculation for an example model mixing pure iron and a 10% lighter iron alloy. The first column describes the adiabatic compression between the base of the magma ocean and the CMB, the second column shows the temperature profile that is then used to calculate the heat content. The third column shows the fully mixed isentropic profile. The first row shows the effect of a_P , for $\lambda = 0.1$ and $f_c = 0.75$. The second row shows the effect of a_P for $\lambda = 5$ and $f_c = 0.75$. The third row shows the effect of f_c for $a_P = 0.5$ and $\lambda = 5$. The orange arrows in the first column shows the adiabatic compression path for a few points in accretion: beginning of accretion (circles), middle of accretion (squares in the third row) and end of accretion (diamonds).

Figure 4. CMB temperature for a post-mixing isentropic core (color scale) for a mix of pure iron core and an iron alloy 10% lighter than pure iron, as a function of parameter \overline{P}_{eq} (x-axis) and f_c (y-axis), for different values of λ (from left to right and top to bottom: $\lambda = 0.1, 1, 2, 3, 4$ and 5). The white areas correspond to the value of \overline{P}_{eq} for a given (f_c, λ) cannot be reached for $a_P \leq 1$. The physical and chemical meaning of the parameter is explained in Section 3.1.2 and in Table 2.

cles). The final pressure of these paths (blue diamond) is the CMB pressure at the time
of metal migration. The red, green, and blue lines show the P, T conditions of metal masses
originating from different magma ocean depths at the end of their migration through the
mantle, for various evolutions of the magma ocean depth (different values of λ , f_c , and
 a_P). The lower pressures correspond to metal masses accreted early, when the Earth was
still small and the CMB pressure low, while higher pressures correspond to metal masses
accreted at the end of Earth's formation.

A key point here is that the adiabatic path $T(P)$ of the metal phase happens to
be less steep than the silicates liquidus. As illustrated in the figures, this implies that
a mass of metal starting from a deeper (higher pressure) magma ocean reaches, at the
same pressure, a higher temperature than a metal mass originating from a shallower magma
ocean.

It also implies that, under these assumptions, the temperature of the core at the
CMB cannot exceed the liquidus of the silicates (estimated at the BSE composition).

(ii) The second column shows the temperature in the core at the end of accretion,
assuming no radial mixing.

This is obtained from the temperature profiles of the first column by taking into
account the additional compression associated with the growth of the planet, from the
CMB pressure at the time of each metal mass addition to the pressure of the same metal
mass when the core is fully formed (Equation 18). The composition of each metal mass
addition is conserved. The core heat content Q_{core} is calculated from this temperature
profile, using Equation 34.

(iii) The third column shows the isentropic temperature profiles obtained with the
assumption of perfect mixing of the temperature profiles shown in the second column,
using the procedure described in section 5.1. The CMB temperatures in the second and
third columns are marked by black circles. In the following, we will focus on the isen-
tropic CMB temperature (third column in Figure 3), but it is interesting to note that
the temperature at the CMB before radial mixing (stratified profile) is different, and usu-
ally higher, than the CMB temperature of the corresponding isentropic profile.

The effect of each of the accretion parameters ($\overline{P_{eq}}$, λ , f_c) with $a_P < 1$ on the CMB
temperature after core mixing is shown in Figure 4. Overall, the effect of these three pa-
rameters can be understood through their effects on the average pressure of equilibra-

502 tion. As explained in point (i) above, a higher pressure of equilibration results in a higher
 503 core temperature, a consequence of the adiabatic path $T(P)$ of the metal being less steep
 504 than the silicates liquidus. Increasing a_P (final equilibration pressure) at fixed f_c and
 505 λ increases on average the equilibration pressure, and therefore increases the core tem-
 506 perature. Increasing f_c (parameter defining both the moment in accretion when P_{eq} in-
 507 crease faster at high λ values and the transition from reduced to oxidized impactor) at
 508 fixed a_P and λ results in a lower pressure of equilibration at $f < f_c$, which results in
 509 a lower core temperature; this is significant only if λ is sufficiently large, since f_c has a
 510 negligible effect on the shape of the equilibration curve at small λ (see Figure 1). Increas-
 511 ing λ (parameter defining the sharpness of the transition from shallow to deep magma
 512 ocean) at fixed a_P and f_c decreases the core temperature, by lowering the equilibration
 513 pressure at $f < f_c$. Overall, for a given composition the temperature variations are within
 514 a 600 K range in this simplified model.

515 **6 Core composition and temperature from geochemically consistent** 516 **accretion models**

517 We now discuss the state of the core resulting from equilibration paths leading to
 518 a geochemically consistent mantle composition. We start with an initial population of
 519 metal/silicates equilibration paths ($P_{eq}(f), T_{eq}(f)$) defined by triplets (a_P, f_c, λ) or, equiv-
 520 alently, $(\overline{P_{eq}}, f_c, \lambda)$. The mantle composition is calculated for each of these equilibration
 521 paths, and compared to the BSE composition model of McDonough and Sun (1995). Only
 522 the equilibration paths yielding a mantle composition consistent with McDonough and
 523 Sun (1995)'s model are conserved. The core composition and thermal state at the end
 524 of accretion are then calculated for each of these geochemically consistent equilibration
 525 paths, using the procedures described in the previous sections.

526 **6.1 Mantle composition**

527 We use a discriminating parameter $\delta^{\overline{BSE}}\chi < 10\%$ for which the calculation is de-
 528 scribed in Supplementary Information S3, in particular in Figure S3 and Table S3. By
 529 definition of this parameter, all the solutions are close enough to the BSE model of McDonough
 530 and Sun (1995) and most of the concentrations, especially the light elements, are within
 531 a 10% range of the BSE. The top panels of Figure 5 show the output (i.e. composition

Figure 5. **Top:** Oxides concentrations in the mantle (major elements on the left, trace elements on the right) as functions of SiO_2 abundance, from accretion histories yielding $\delta^{\overline{BSE}\chi} < 10\%$. The colored solid lines represent the BSE concentrations in the reference model, with a 10% variation. The grey vertical line is the upper limit of $\chi_{\text{SiO}_2}^{BSE} \pm 10\%$. **Bottom:** Composition of the core (major elements on the left, trace elements on the right) as a function of Fe abundance, from accretion histories yielding $\delta^{\overline{BSE}\chi} < 10\%$.

532 that meet the requirement $\delta^{\overline{BSE}\chi} < 10\%$) mantle composition range compared to the
 533 reference model.

534 6.2 Geochemically consistent equilibration paths

535 The geochemical filter we apply to the core-formation model selects a subset of triplets
 536 (a_P, f_c, λ) – or, equivalently, $(\overline{P_{eq}}, f_c, \lambda)$ – which defines equilibration paths $(P_{eq}(f), T_{eq}(f))$
 537 giving a mantle composition that is consistent with Earth’s mantle composition. For clar-
 538 ity, in the rest of the text we will use $\overline{P_{eq}}$ instead of a_P . $\overline{P_{eq}}$ being indicative of the over-
 539 all equilibrium pressure, while a_P is only representative of the pressure at the end of ac-
 540 cretion. Within this subset, the parameters are correlated, as shown by the correlation

Figure 6. Correlation matrix of the variables $\overline{P_{eq}}$, f_c , λ , Si+O concentration (% wt.), and CMB temperature after core mixing, calculated from the accretion histories yielding $\overline{\delta^{BSE}\chi} < 10\%$. The physical and chemical meaning of the parameters is explained in Section 3.1.2 and in Table 2.

Figure 7. Range of $(\overline{P_{eq}}, f_c, \lambda)$ triplets yielding an Earth-like BSE concentration. From left to right: $\overline{P_{eq}}$ vs f_c , $\overline{P_{eq}}$ vs λ and f_c vs λ . The color scale shows the values of the third parameter. The physical and chemical meaning of the parameters is explained in Section 3.1.2 and in Table 2.

541 matrix of Figure 6 and illustrated in more details in Figure 7. Changing one parame-
 542 ter requires changing the others so as to keep a geochemically coherent model.

543 The geochemical filter allows values of λ (parameter defining the sharpness of the
 544 transition from shallow to deep magma ocean) within the full range of explored values
 545 (Figure 7 and Figure S5), and is therefore not discriminating for this parameter. How-
 546 ever, high values of λ correlate with low values of f_c (i.e more oxidized composition and
 547 a more rapid transition to a deep magma ocean) and $\overline{P_{eq}}$ (i.e. the final magma ocean
 548 depth tends to be lower at higher values of λ).

549 The parameters $\overline{P_{eq}}$ and f_c (parameter defining both the moment in accretion when
 550 P_{eq} increase faster at high λ values and the transition from reduced to oxidized impactor)
 551 are the most affected by the geochemical filter, since only a subrange of the sampled set
 552 yields consistent BSE compositions. Successful accretion models have $\overline{P_{eq}}$ between 20
 553 GPa and 45 GPa, and f_c between 0.6 and 1. Higher values of f_c are compensated by higher
 554 value of $\overline{P_{eq}}$: the more reduced accretion is, the deeper the magma ocean needs to be to
 555 fit the BSE composition. For f_c values close to 1, the values of $\overline{P_{eq}}$ are always higher than
 556 40 GPa (corresponding to a_P always higher than 0.6), and only $\lambda < 1$ can fit the BSE.
 557 Reduced accretion is therefore possible only for accretion scenarios in which a very deep
 558 magma ocean ($P_{eq} > 0.6P_{CMB}$) is maintained during the entire accretion.

559 **6.3 Core composition**

560 The core compositions of the successful differentiation models are shown on the bot-
 561 tom panels of Figure 5. The range of core composition is consistent with previous mod-
 562 els of accretion (Fischer et al., 2015; Badro et al., 2018; Clesi et al., 2016; Boujibar et
 563 al., 2014): in all cases we get Fe-Ni alloy representing $\sim 80 - 90$ % of the mass, with
 564 Si and O representing ≤ 10 % of the mass, consistent with the core density deficit al-
 565 lowing 10 % of light elements (Dziewonski & Anderson, 1981). This is the case partic-
 566 ularly for the higher values of $\overline{P_{eq}}$ (40- 45 GPa, Figure 8). V, Cr and Co are trace ele-
 567 ments that have a negligible effect on density compared to the four other elements.

568 The concentration of Fe ranges from 85.5% wt and 90.5%wt, while the concentra-
 569 tion of Ni ranges from 5.2 to 6.04 %wt. The concentrations of Fe and Ni are positively
 570 correlated. The major light element in the core is found to be Si, with a concentration
 571 ranging from 1.5 to 6 % wt. Oxygen is less abundant, but not negligible, with a concen-

572 tration ranging from 0.97 to 2.0% wt. The concentrations of Si and O are positively cor-
 573 related. However, Si concentration is always higher than the O concentration, which is
 574 consistent with the results of Ricolleau et al. (2011) and Tsuno et al. (2013). This is ex-
 575 plained by the fact that for most of accretion, while the values of K_d^{Si} are lower than the
 576 values of K_d^O , the final partitioning coefficient for Si is a function of $\frac{\chi_{Fe}}{\chi_{FeO}}^2$ while the par-
 577 titioning of O is dependant on $\frac{\chi_{Fe}}{\chi_{Mw}}$ with $\chi_{Fe} \gg \chi_{FeO}$ and $\chi_{Mw} > \chi_{FeO}$ (Frost et
 578 al., 2010). Therefore, balancing the mass when the environment is reduced tends to lower
 579 the spread between the Nernst partitioning coefficient of Si and the partitioning coef-
 580 ficient of O in the same P-T conditions, while the spread is bit higher for oxidized con-
 581 ditions. Since χ_{SiO_2} is higher than χ_{FeO} (especially in a reduced environment), the mass
 582 effect tends to favor Si in metal rather than O. An illustration of this effect where from
 583 a high difference in K_d values we get lower difference in partitioning coefficient which
 584 yield a favorable incorporation of Si over O in the metal is presented in Figure S2. The
 585 incorporation of O is favored during oxidizing phase of accretion, but as shown in Fig-
 586 ure 7, the amount of oxidized impactor always represent less than 40% of accretion ($f_c \geq$
 587 0.6)

588 The correlation matrix of Figure 6 and the top panels of Figure 8 show how the
 589 core composition correlates with the accretion parameters. The variations of $\overline{P_{eq}}$ explain
 590 most of the variance of the core composition. This strong positive correlation simply re-
 591 flects the effect of pressure on the partitioning behavior of Si and O, which become more
 592 siderophile at higher pressure. The correlations between the core composition and f_c (pa-
 593 rameter defining both the moment in accretion when P_{eq} increase faster at high λ val-
 594 ues and the transition from reduced to oxidized impactor) and λ (parameter defining the
 595 sharpness of the transition from shallow to deep magma ocean) results mostly from the
 596 correlations between $\overline{P_{eq}}$, f_c and λ discussed in section 6.2, and are therefore of less sig-
 597 nificance.

598 6.4 Core temperature

599 6.4.1 Effect of $\overline{P_{eq}}$, f_c and λ on T_{CMB}^{is}

600 Figure 8 (bottom panel) shows T_{CMB}^{is} as a function of $\overline{P_{eq}}$, f_c (parameter defining
 601 both the moment in accretion when P_{eq} increase faster at high λ values and the tran-
 602 sition from reduced to oxidized impactor) and λ (parameter defining the sharpness of

Figure 8. **Top:** Light element concentrations (O and Si in % wt) in the core as a function of a_P (left), f_c (center) and λ (right). The color scale shows the value of f_c on the left panel, and a_P on the center and right panel. **Bottom:** $T_{\text{CMB}}^{\text{is}}$ (Equation 37) as a function of $\overline{P_{eq}}$ (left), f_c (center) and λ (right). The color scale shows the values of f_c (left) and $\overline{P_{eq}}$ (centre and right) of each point. The physical and chemical meaning of the parameters is explained in Section 3.1.2 and in Table 2.

Figure 9. Value of $T_{\text{CMB}}^{\text{is}}$ as a function of $\overline{P_{eq}}$ for different values of ε . ε is varying between 0 and 0.25. The y-axis values are in 1000 K. The physical and chemical meaning of the parameters is explained in Section 3.1.2 and in Table 2.

603 the transition from shallow to deep magma ocean), assuming no dissipation in the metal
 604 phase, and negligible heat transfer between the metal and surrounding silicates. The cor-
 605 relation coefficients between $T_{\text{CMB}}^{\text{is}}$ and other parameters are given by the correlation ma-
 606 trix of Figure 6. The CMB temperature we obtain ranges from 3925 to 4150 K, which
 607 is consistent with some estimates the present-day CMB temperature (e.g. Nomura et al.,
 608 2014). The lowest estimate in our range is close to the present-day temperature but it
 609 should be higher because we neglected the effect of heat production elements. See Sec-
 610 tion 7.3.3 for more on the heat production.

611 The CMB temperature correlates positively with $\overline{P_{eq}}$, as expected from the discus-
 612 sion of section 5.2. The counter-intuitive positive correlation between $T_{\text{CMB}}^{\text{is}}$ and f_c can
 613 be explained by the positive correlation between $\overline{P_{eq}}$ and f_c among the equilibration paths
 614 consistent with the geochemical constraints. $T_{\text{CMB}}^{\text{is}}$ correlates negatively with λ , which
 615 is consistent with both the anti-correlation between $\overline{P_{eq}}$ and λ , and the effect of λ on the
 616 core temperature found in section 5.2. Note also the quite strong positive correlation be-
 617 tween the temperature of the core and the abundance of Si and O.

6.4.2 *Effect of dissipative heating in the metal phase*

Adding dissipative heating to the metal phase during its descent through the mantle increases the core temperature as shown on Figure 9. This is a logical results of adding more heat to the metallic diapir during its descent to form the core. The final temperature profile after compression (Equation 19) is therefore calculated from an hotter temperature profile. The effect of dissipation is strongest at the lowest values of $\overline{P_{eq}}$: at $\overline{P_{eq}} = 20$ GPa, assuming $\epsilon = 0.25$ multiplies T_{CMB}^{is} by ~ 1.6 (Figure 9) compared to the $\epsilon = 0$ case, corresponding to temperatures up to 6500 K. At the highest value of $\overline{P_{eq}}$, the core temperature at $\epsilon = 0.25$ is ~ 1000 K higher than at $\epsilon = 0$. The fact that dissipative heating has more effect at lower values of $\overline{P_{eq}}$ can be explained by the largest distance travelled on average by the metal through the mantle. This implies that the migration of the metal from the base of the magma ocean to the CMB induces a larger change of gravitational energy, thus resulting in more dissipative heating.

These results are consistent with the 'hot core' hypothesis (King & Olson, 2011), but are dependent on the amount of dissipation energy going into the mantle. In this study we did not focus on the mechanisms of transfer of dissipative heating, and modeled directly the amount of heat transfered to the core. However, this amount is largely dependent on the mechanism of formation, and is likely low ($\epsilon < 15\%$). The probable values of ϵ is discussed further in section 7.2.

7 Discussion

The results presented in the previous section are compatible with previous estimates of the temperature at the core-mantle boundary (e.g. Nomura et al., 2014), even though our results are in the lower end of the different estimates (see for instance Labrosse, 2015, and references therein). Adding large amount of dissipation increases the core heat content, towards the hot core models, such as King and Olson (2011) model. Our model therefore shows that classical accretion models based on siderophile partitioning can be combined with thermal evolution model in order to put constraints on the heat content of the core and its subsequent evolution.

646 7.1 Choice of equation of state and Grüneisen parameter

647 The equation of state of liquid metal has a strong influence on the results. From
648 Figure 2, we can see that a variety of equation of state for the core have been proposed.

649 This is due to the fact that measuring liquid metal density in high-pressure exper-
650 iments (Morard et al., 2013; Sanloup et al., 2000; Kuwayama et al., 2020) is a compli-
651 cated problem (hence higher error bars), and is achieved to relatively low pressure rel-
652 atively to the Earth’s core pressures. The ab initio data (Ichikawa et al., 2014; Umem-
653 oto et al., 2014) tend to overestimate the temperature reached in the core, yielding some
654 error in the fit. Shock wave experiments (Anderson & Ahrens, 1994; Zhang et al., 2018)
655 on the other hand follow an hugoniot, rendering the results harder to be reconciled with
656 the other experimental data.

657 The Murnaghan equation of state we chose is closer to the PREM data for pure
658 iron with 8.5% wt of light elements and Kuwayama et al. (2020) data, therefore getting
659 an easy to use EOS and analytical solution. Vinet equation of state (Irving et al., 2018),
660 or Mie-Grüneisen (Kuwayama et al., 2020) are not as simple to use and do not yield an-
661 alytical solutions to our equations, while providing a very little added value for our model.
662 Further work leading to a better understanding of the equation of state for liquid metal
663 at higher pressure and their dependence on metal composition (especially the presence
664 of oxygen) would be an enhancement of our models.

665 A second limitation to our model is the choice of Grüneisen parameter formalism.
666 We chose to follow the formalism of Al’Tshuler et al. (1987) with the values proposed
667 by Dewaele et al. (2006). A first limitation of this formalism is that there is no compo-
668 sitional dependence of the Grüneisen parameter. Studies focus on pure iron (mostly solid)
669 behaviour (Al’Tshuler et al., 1987; Dubrovinsky et al., 2000; Dewaele et al., 2006; Doro-
670 gokupets et al., 2017). These studies yield different values for γ_∞ and γ_0 , between 0.9
671 and 1.2 and between 1.8 and 2.05 respectively (Dubrovinsky et al., 2000, and references
672 therein). Decreasing the value of γ_∞ tend to increase the temperature of the core. This
673 is due to a higher value of the $\gamma_0 - \gamma_\infty$, therefore leading to a higher value of T given
674 by Equation 32. Increasing the value of γ_0 also leads to lower temperature, by increas-
675 ing the value of β in Equation 32. The compositional dependency of γ_0 and γ_∞ has not
676 been properly studied for the composition relevant to the Earth’s core. The value of Dewaele
677 et al. (2006) used in this study yield γ values relevant with pressure change: γ decreases
678 toward γ_∞ value at higher pressures, and increases toward γ_0 value at lower pressure.

679 At the CMB pressure, depending on composition, $\gamma \sim 1.45$, significantly different than
 680 the constant $\gamma \sim 1.7$ used in other studies of the core (e.g. Anderson & Ahrens, 1994;
 681 Labrosse, 2015), but expected when studying the behaviour of iron at high pressure (Dubrovinsky
 682 et al., 2000).

683 Finally, the formalism we use to describe $\gamma(P)$ behaviour differs from the formal-
 684 ism adopted by Kuwayama et al. (2020): $\gamma = \gamma_0 \left(\frac{\rho_0}{\rho}\right)^b$, with $\gamma_0 = 2.02$ and $b = 0.63$.
 685 With this formalism, the ratio $\left(\frac{\rho(P)}{\rho_{P_{eq}}}\right)^{\gamma_\infty}$ disappears from Equation 32. It yields a tem-
 686 perature range significantly higher than our models, between 4130 and 4280 K (see Fig-
 687 ure S7). The discrepancy between our results and the calculation of Kuwayama et al.
 688 (2020) can be explained by the fact that their equation of state and γ formalism are fit-
 689 ted at the same time, yielding a value of $b = 0.63$ valid for their equation of state in
 690 the scope of their study, but that need to be refined for our conditions of calculation.

691 To summarize, better understanding of the equation of state of liquid metal with
 692 light elements has to be done, in parallel of a tuning of the Grüneisen parameter with
 693 the equation of state and composition of the metal. Such a combination would greatly
 694 improve our understanding of the thermal state of the core.

695 **7.2 Range of dissipation energy transfered to the core**

696 Our model without dissipation favors a relatively cold core, with a $T_{\text{CMB}}^{\text{is}}$ between
 697 3925 K and 4150 K (Figure 8, bottom panels). Adding a large amount of dissipative en-
 698 ergy to the metal phase sinking into the core can yield very high temperatures (up to
 699 6500 K, Figure 9). However, the amount of dissipative energy transferred to the metal
 700 (ε in our model) is dependent on the mechanism of formation. When considering the likely
 701 mechanisms of core formation, the values shown in Figure 9 for $\varepsilon > 0.1$ can be seen as
 702 irrelevant, for the reasons detailed below.

703 One way to incorporate high amounts of dissipative energy in the metal is by the
 704 formation of a trail conduit in the silicate, which allows the dissipation energy to be trans-
 705 ferred to small metal droplet (King & Olson, 2011). Even in this case, not 100% of the
 706 dissipative energy is transferred to the metal, with an efficiency of 60 % after King and
 707 Olson (2011), corresponding to a ε value of 0.6 in our study. In this scenario, the tem-
 708 perature of the core is highly dependent on the accretion style: continuous increases of
 709 the magma ocean depth ($\lambda < 1$ and $\lambda \sim 1$, $\overline{P_{eq}} > 30$ GPa), $T_{\text{CMB}}^{\text{is}}$ would be around 8

710 000 K; while a shallow magma ocean followed by a dramatic increase of the magma ocean
 711 depth ($\lambda > 2$, $\overline{P_{eq}} < 30$ GPa) yields temperature closer to 10 000 K. However, these
 712 temperatures are valid only if a trail conduit is formed and a substantial part of the metal-
 713 lic diapir is broken into droplets of 10 cm (Olson & Weeraratne, 2008). At these diapirs
 714 sizes, there is some heat loss to the mantle (see Supplementary Information S4) which
 715 would tend to lower the temperature. Furthermore, in our model we considered that all
 716 the metal is affected by the super adiabatic heating, while in the model of King and Ol-
 717 son (2011) only 40% of the metal is affected. If we neglect the effect of composition and
 718 apply a ratio of 40% of the metal affected by the dissipation throughout the accretion,
 719 a raw calculation gives a maximum temperature of 6000K for a global heat content 2.25
 720 times higher than a in a non-dissipation case, those values correspond to $\varepsilon = 0.25$ and
 721 $\lambda > 4$ in our models (Figure 9). Even in a favorable case, the amount of actual dissi-
 722 pation energy incorporated in the metal is 25%.

723 If the formation of the core is happening without a trail conduit in the silicate, then
 724 the amount of dissipation energy is even lower. Core formation by diapirism favors vis-
 725 cous heating and dissipation of energy in the mantle rather than the metal (Ke & Solo-
 726 matov, 2009; Monteux et al., 2009; Samuel et al., 2010). In this case, only a very small
 727 fraction of the dissipation energy goes into the metal (section 2.2.2). The formation of
 728 diapir by Rayleigh-Taylor instability is very efficient (e.g. Olson & Weeraratne, 2008).
 729 Therefore, it is most probable than the effect of gravitational dissipation is limited. How-
 730 ever, even small amount of dissipative heat in the metal (5%, Figure 9) can mask the
 731 effect of the accretion style on the temperature that is discussed below.

732 **7.3 Composition of the mantle, accretion style and core thermal state**

733 ***7.3.1 Accretion style and composition***

734 The composition of the mantle (Figure 5, top panels) yields a range of values for
 735 the parameter chosen in this study (Figures S4 and S5). In particular, the maximum pres-
 736 sure of equilibration (a_P) and the amount of reduced material (determined by param-
 737 eter f_c) are the main parameters which have influencing the composition. Therefore, an
 738 accretion scenario fitting the BSE model has to have the following characteristics: (i) a
 739 final pressure of metal/silicate segregation between 40 and 60 % of the CMB pressure
 740 (i.e. 55 to 80 GPa, corresponding to a maximum extent of the magma ocean between

741 1200 and 1800 km) and an average pressure of equilibrium between 20 and 50 GPa, cor-
 742 responding to a mean 25 to 60 % of the mean CMB pressure; (ii) a majority (between
 743 60 and 80%) of the accreted material has to be reduced, with oxidized material accret-
 744 ing at the end of accretion. These results confirms previous studies on metal/silicate par-
 745 titioning: the pressure of equilibration around 50% of P_{CMB} resulting in a magma ocean
 746 maximal depth of 1800 km, especially at the end of accretion, is a classical results nec-
 747 cessary to explain Ni and Co abundances in the BSE (M. Bouhifd & Jephcoat, 2011; Siebert
 748 et al., 2012; Fischer et al., 2015; Badro et al., 2015). The accretion of reduced material
 749 yielded by our model is coherent with most of the studies of Earth’s accretion at the ex-
 750 ception of Siebert et al. (2013).

751 As shown in Figure S5, the highest number of solutions is for f_c between 0.7 and
 752 0.8, but 30 solutions have been obtained by accreting 90 to 100% of reduced material.
 753 These solutions, especially 100% reduced accretion (n=6), are at odds with previous mod-
 754 els (Tuff et al., 2011; Fischer et al., 2015; Rubie et al., 2015) and with the results of N-
 755 Body simulations (e.g. Morbidelli et al., 2000; O’Brien et al., 2014; Izidoro et al., 2021)
 756 which need to accrete at least some more oxidized material at the end of accretion. How-
 757 ever, these solutions only work for $\overline{P_{eq}} > 45$ GPa ($a_P > 0.6$) and $\lambda < 1$, which means
 758 that in order to have 100% reduced impactor material, the pressure of equilibration has
 759 to be high all along the accretion. Therefore these results can be explained by the fact
 760 that oxygen fugacity tend to increase in magma with pressure (Armstrong et al., 2019,
 761 and references therein), and also by the limited number of element fitted in the model.
 762 Indeed, adding more f_{O_2} sensitive elements such as Nb and Ta (Tuff et al., 2011; Cartier,
 763 Hammouda, Doucelance, et al., 2014; Cartier, Hammouda, Boyet, et al., 2014) would have
 764 certainly help constrain the redox evolution of the planet and possibly eliminated the
 765 solutions $f_c > 0.9$, which are highly unlikely to be correct.

766 **7.3.2 Accretion style and thermal state of the core**

767 From Figure 8, we can see that a_P and f_c (parameter defining both the moment
 768 in accretion when P_{eq} increase faster at high λ values and the transition from reduced
 769 to oxidized impactor) have some effect on the heat content and temperature of the core.

770 Models of accretion where the depth of magma ocean is high will tend to favor hot-
 771 ter cores: for instance the models of Rubie et al. (2015) yields maximum pressure of equi-

772 liberation between 72 and 80% of the CMB pressure would give higher CMB tempera-
 773 tures than models where the maximum pressure is set at 66% of the CMB pressure as
 774 in Fischer et al. (2015). Indeed, in the models of of (Rubie et al., 2015), the close equiv-
 775 alent parameter in our models would be $a_P \sim 0.72 - 0.8$, $f_c \simeq 0.93 - 0.99$ and $\lambda = 1$,
 776 which would yield $\overline{P_{eq}} = 45$ GPa and therefore $T_{CMB}^{is} > 4100$ K if we continue the
 777 trend of 8. In the case of Fischer et al. (2015), the closest equivalent parameter in our
 778 models would be $a_P = 0.66$, $f_c = 0.75$ and $\lambda = 1$, which yield $\overline{P_{eq}} = 38$ GPa, and an
 779 isentropic temperature at the CMB between 4000 and 4100 K. The comparison is eas-
 780 ily in the latter case, because the chemical models are more similar.

781 A parameter controlling the heat content and temperature at the end of accretion,
 782 for a given composition range, is λ (parameter defining the sharpness of the transition
 783 from shallow to deep magma ocean). Increasing the value of this parameter leads to a
 784 decrease in temperature, for every case studied here (Figure 8) This means that mod-
 785 els of accretion for which a deep magma ocean exists all along the accretion's process
 786 (e.g. Wood et al., 2008; Boujibar et al., 2014; Fischer et al., 2015; Rubie et al., 2015; Clesi
 787 et al., 2016) are favoring relatively high T_{CMB}^{is} , between 4000 and 4150 K after mixing,
 788 depending on the value of λ and ε . The temperature becomes higher if heat transfer to
 789 the mantle is a minor process (i.e. large diapir leading to large values of Pe number),
 790 and compression of the metal and gravitational dissipation ($\varepsilon > 0.1$) are the main pro-
 791 cesses controlling the core temperature.

792 On the other hand, models with large impacts at the end of accretion (e.g. Canup,
 793 2004; Raymond et al., 2009; Grewal et al., 2019) leading to a rapid increase of magma
 794 ocean depth after a long period of shallow magma ocean ($\lambda \sim 3 - 5$ in our models),
 795 will favor lower core temperatures. This is because the adiabatic path followed by the
 796 metal is less steep than the liquidus of silicate (Figures 3, 4 and 8). Therefore the com-
 797 pression of the metallic diapir and the metallic core is not enough to compensate for the
 798 initial lower temperature of the metal during the shallow magma ocean stage. However,
 799 this effect can be erase if relatively high amounts of gravitational dissipation energy are
 800 transferred in the metal: as shown in Figure 9, the trend in temperature evolution shown
 801 in Figure 8 (Bottom row) is reversed for $\varepsilon > 0.05$. Therefore, models that propose core/mantle
 802 segregation in a shallow magma ocean followed by large impacts need to incorporate at
 803 least 5% of gravitational dissipation energy to produce core as hot as models that have
 804 a deep magma ocean all along the accretion.

805 If compression and dissipation are the main process controlling the temperature,
 806 this type of scenarios leads to $T_{\text{CMB}}^{\text{is}} \sim 3950$ K for compression only, and higher tem-
 807 peratures if $\varepsilon \neq 0$, up to 6500 K for $\varepsilon = 0.25$ and more probably ≤ 5000 K for $\varepsilon <$
 808 0.1.

809 Overall, the CMB temperature of the core, even after mixing, are in the lower end
 810 of the proposed temperature of the core obtained from different authors (King & Olson,
 811 2011; Labrosse, 2015), and closer, but still higher, to the one determined by the solidus
 812 of pyrolite (Nomura et al., 2014). While adding a dissipation terms during the core for-
 813 mation does increases the temperature by 15%, it is still not enough to account for the
 814 relatively high temperatures proposed by several authors (up to 7000 K for King & Ol-
 815 son, 2011; Labrosse, 2015). One explanation may lie in the energy required to mix the
 816 core, which can change the overall heat budget of the core (Section 7.5.2).

817 **7.3.3 Effect of Heat producing elements**

818 As stated in Section 6.4, the temperature yielded by our models without any dis-
 819 sipation energy incorporation into the core ranges from 3925 K to 4150 K. The lowest
 820 values are close to the current estimates of CMB temperature (Nomura et al., 2014). One
 821 would expect, because of secular cooling, higher temperatures at the CMB in the early
 822 Earth than the temperature of today's CMB.

823 Our calculations ignore the possible effect of radioactive heating, and we estimate
 824 here the contribution of heat producing element (HPE) to the heat content of the core
 825 at the end of its formation. The main element producing heat in the core is K (Corgne
 826 et al., 2007; M. A. Bouhifd et al., 2007; Watanabe et al., 2014). U and Th concentra-
 827 tions in the core are low (~ 1.2 ppb and ~ 5 ppb for U and Th, respectively, according
 828 to Faure et al., 2020) due to their lithophile behavior, and combined with long half-life,
 829 their contribution to the heat content of the early core is negligible.

830 The range of K concentration depends on the O concentration of the core (Corgne
 831 et al., 2007; M. A. Bouhifd et al., 2007; Watanabe et al., 2014; Faure et al., 2020), rang-
 832 ing from <1 ppm to ~ 80 ppm for 0% wt and 9 % wt of O in the core, respectively. Our
 833 models yield low O concentrations (~ 2 %wt), which translates in a K concentration around
 834 40 ppm. Using 40 ppm of K in the core, the heat production rate of 1.917×10^{-5} W.kg $^{-1}$
 835 from Weast et al. (1988), the [present-day](#) proportion of ^{40}K in total K of 0.0117% from

836 De Laeter et al. (2003), which translates in a proportion of 0.14% during core formation
 837 4.56 Gy ago (using a decay constant $\lambda_{40\text{K}} = 0.55 \text{ Gy}^{-1}$), and a timescale of core for-
 838 mation between 30 and 100 millions years (Kleine et al., 2009), the supplementary heat
 839 content due to ^{40}K decay ranges from $\sim 2.0 \times 10^{27} \text{ J}$ to $\sim 6.7 \times 10^{27} \text{ J}$.

840 Even with 80 ppm of K in the core (highest estimate from Corgne et al., 2007), we
 841 would get for a core forming in 100 millions years an additional $1.3 \times 10^{28} \text{ J}$, ~ 100 times
 842 less than the heat content of the core we have estimated.

843 Therefore the assumption that we can neglect the heat producing elements in es-
 844 timating the temperature of the early core is valid; adding K, U and Th into the chem-
 845 ical model would not yield significantly different results.

846 After core formation, radioactive heating could only induce an increase of the core
 847 temperature if the radioactive heat production exceeds the heat flux at the CMB. This
 848 seems unlikely since the radioactive heat production in the core is likely modest even 4.56
 849 Gy ago (around 2 TW with 40 ppm of K in the core, about 12 times higher than it is
 850 today). Radioactive heating is therefore unlikely to help reconcile models yielding low
 851 core temperatures with its present-day estimate.

852 **7.4 Using early core temperature as a constraining parameter for core** 853 **composition**

854 With the simplifying hypothesis described in Section 4 and no dissipative heating
 855 in the metal, the predictions of T_{CMB}^{is} obtained with our model are all in the same range
 856 as the estimates of the current CMB temperature. Some of the geochemically consistent
 857 scenarios yield CMB temperatures that are lower than the current estimates. This can
 858 be interpreted in different ways:

- 859 i) The equation of state of liquid metal (Equation 29) and the value of Grüneisen
 860 parameter (Equation 31) are poorly chosen and leads to an underestimation of the
 861 metal temperature during compression. As discussed in section 7.1, the core tem-
 862 perature is indeed quite sensitive to the choice of equation of state formalism and
 863 parameters.
- 864 ii) Giant impacts that do not equilibrate with the magma ocean (core-merging pro-
 865 cess) can lead to higher temperature of the metal accreting to the core at the end

866 of the core formation (Canup, 2004; Suer et al., 2021). Since our model does not
 867 take this hypothesis into account, the temperatures predicted by the model may
 868 be underestimated.

869 iii) The radioactive heat production within the core is larger than the heat flux at the
 870 CMB for some time after core formation, resulting in an increase of the temper-
 871 ature of the core. This is however highly unlikely, as discussed in Section 7.3.3.

872 iv) All of the previous hypothesis have been taken into account (strong confidence in
 873 equation of state, giant impacts and incorporation of heat producing elements)
 874 and the temperature is still lower than the current CMB temperature. In such a
 875 case, despite the model being consistent chemically, it is not thermally consistent
 876 and therefore can be discarded

877 If interpretation iv) can be used for our model or any other similar model of core-mantle
 878 segregation, then it is possible to discard core-formation scenarios and core compositions
 879 on the basis of the core temperature, despite the composition being chemically accurate
 880 in regards to the BSE. Core temperature could then become one more parameter used
 881 to constrain the core composition and core-formation processes, thanks to the positive
 882 correlation predicted by the model between light elements concentration, core temper-
 883 ature, and mean equilibration pressure (Figure 8).

884 **7.5 Core composition and primordial chemical stratification**

885 In this section we propose some interpretations on how we can accrete a stratified
 886 core (Jacobson et al., 2017) into a well mixed core and the potential energy variation as-
 887 sociated with it.

888 ***7.5.1 Compositional stratification of the core***

889 Our results yield a range of bulk compositions for the core that are in agreement
 890 with previous studies: $\sim 90\%$ of Fe-Ni alloy combined with $\sim 10\%$ of light elements, in
 891 our case Si and O (Figure 5, bottom panels). Since the core formed in several steps, it
 892 can end up being chemically and thermally stratified, depending on the degree of mix-
 893 ing which may follow the formation of the core (Jacobson et al., 2017; Landeau et al.,
 894 2017).

Figure 10. Evolution of the light element content in the core for all the solutions of our model as a function of normalized core radius ($R_{\text{core}} = 3470 \text{ km}$). Top left: χ_{Si} (% wt). Top right: χ_{O} (% wt). Bottom left: $\chi_{\text{Si}} + \chi_{\text{O}}$. Bottom right: $\rho_{\text{core}} (10^3 \text{ kg.m}^{-3})$. Each line is a solution of the model corresponding to the bulk composition shown in Figure 5.

895 Figure 10 shows that the bulk compositions we obtain cover a large range of possible stratifications. Locally, the sum of Si and O concentrations can be up to 20% wt
 896 (bottom panel, Figure 10), while the overall bulk core concentration is still less than 10%
 897 wt (Figure 5, bottom panels). Another feature of the stratified model is that the center
 898 of the core is less rich in light elements, due to a lower pressure of equilibration and
 899 thus a lower value for K_d for both element. The concentration in light element increases
 900 toward the CMB, since the metal close to the CMB equilibrated with silicates at higher
 901 pressures. The main light element is silicon, which gets incorporated earlier in the ac-
 902 cretion history. Oxygen becomes a more prominent element at the end of accretion, for
 903 more oxidizing impactors; its concentration is therefore high only in the upper part of
 904 the core. The concentration of Si drops once the condition of accretion are more oxidiz-
 905 ing, leading to more oxygen being incorporated in the core. This behaviour is expected
 906 since Si and O tend to exclude each other in the metallic melt (Frost et al., 2010; Ricol-
 907 leau et al., 2011). The stratification is therefore not smooth, and can be non-monotonic:
 908 though the concentration profile is stably stratified in most of the core, there is often a
 909 region where it is unstably stratified (concentration of light elements increasing with depth).
 910 The concentration in light elements often reaches its maximum a few hundred kilome-
 911 ters below the CMB ($R \sim 2500\text{-}3000$ km).

913 The chemical stratification could be conserved in the current core (Bouffard et al.,
 914 2020; Landeau et al., 2021), but for the rest of the paper we will focus on the implica-
 915 tions of going from a stratified core as given by our models to a fully mixed core for which
 916 we calculated the isentropic temperature.

917 ***7.5.2 Variations of potential energy and implications for core mixing*** 918 ***processes***

Going from a stratified profile to a mixed profile changes the potential energy of the core, which is

$$E_p = 4\pi \int_0^{R_{\text{CMB}}} g(r)\rho(r)r^3 dr \quad (38)$$

919 (Birch, 1965; Flasar & Birch, 1973), where $g(r)$ is the gravitational field in the core given
 920 by interpolation of the density profile and integration of the Gauss theorem for gravi-
 921 tation. The total potential energy for both model (stratified and mixed) is shown in Fig-
 922 ure S8 and S9, and ranges from ~ 3.8 to $4.7 \cdot 10^{31}$ J for both profiles. The variation of

Figure 11. $\Delta E = E_p^{\text{strati}} - E_p^{\text{mixed}}$ calculated from Equation 38 for the density profiles obtained at the end of accretion (E_p^{strati} , Figure 10) and after core mixing (E_p^{mixed}), as a function of \overline{P}_{eq} , f_c , λ and $\chi_{\text{Si+O}}$. The black line separate negative value from positive value. The physical and chemical meaning of the parameters is explained in Section 3.1.2 and in Table 2.

923 potential energy between the stratified and mixed situations is calculated as $\Delta E = E_p^{\text{strati}} -$
 924 E_p^{mixed} . If $\Delta E < 0$, then the potential energy of the mixed profile is higher than the
 925 potential energy of the initial stratified profile, which means that mixing the core would
 926 require an energy input. If $\Delta E > 0$, then mixing the core would lead to a release of en-
 927 ergy, and would therefore be energetically favored.

928 Figure 11 shows that the variation in potential energy is between -1.32×10^{29} J and
 929 0.96×10^{29} J, corresponding to $\sim \pm 1\%$ of the total potential energy of the core (Fig-
 930 ure S8 and S9). Most of our models (76%) yield $\Delta E < 0$, but a significant number (24
 931 %, 117 models) of solutions yield $\Delta E > 0$. One could have expected ΔE to be always
 932 negative, corresponding to monotonically stably stratified profiles, but as shown on Fig-
 933 ure 10, the concentration profile, though stably stratified in most of the core, is often un-
 934 stably stratified in a region a few hundred kilometers below the CMB. ΔE can be either

935 negative or positive depending on the relative importance of the stably and unstably strat-
 936 ified regions.

937 Figure 11 shows no clear trend between ΔE and the values of $\overline{P_{eq}}$, f_c (parameter
 938 defining both the moment in accretion when P_{eq} increase faster at high λ values and the
 939 transition from reduced to oxidized impactor), λ (parameter defining the sharpness of
 940 the transition from shallow to deep magma ocean) or the light element concentrations.
 941 As shown in Section 7.5.1, the uppermost 20 to 30% of the core (2500- 3470 km) is where
 942 the variations in light element concentrations are the most important. Since it is also
 943 where $g(r)$ is the highest, this region is the controlling factor of the potential energy change.
 944 In 25% of the case, the combination of light element concentration changes with the grav-
 945 itational field can create a high enough gravitational instability in the core to yield pos-
 946 itive ΔE . It shows that incorporation of oxygen in the core, proposed by several authors
 947 (Frost et al., 2010; Ricolleau et al., 2011; Fischer et al., 2015) can facilitate to some ex-
 948 tent the mixing of the core, and participate, at least to some extent, to the destruction
 949 of a core stratification (Landeau et al., 2016; Bouffard et al., 2020).

950 When $\Delta E > 0$, partial or complete mixing of the core may still arise due to ex-
 951 ternal mechanical forcing resulting from giant impacts. The energy release by a giant
 952 impact, as estimated by Lock et al. (2020) or Carter et al. (2020), may be in the range
 953 of 10^{31} to 10^{32} J, much larger than the $\sim 10^{29}$ J energy variation needed to mix the core.
 954 The fraction of this energy available to mix the core is difficult to estimate, as recognized
 955 by Jacobson et al. (2017) and (Bouffard et al., 2020), but we note that mixing the core
 956 necessitates only a few % of the kinetic energy release by a Moon-forming giant impact.
 957 This is consistent with the Jacobson et al. (2017) model, which takes a fraction of 4%
 958 from the initial impactor energy release, as well as Bouffard et al. (2020) who proposed
 959 an energy transfer to the core corresponding to 0.5 to 1% of the impactor energy release.
 960 These amount are kinetic energy are an upper bound, since it possible to mix some of
 961 the core everytime some metal reaches the core (Landeau et al., 2016).

962 8 Conclusion

963 In this study we build a parameterized model of accretion linking the core temper-
 964 ature with the composition of the mantle. The model successfully proves that it is pos-
 965 sible to link the core temperature at the end of accretion to the core composition, pro-
 966 vided a certain number of parameters are sufficiently known (Equations of state, silicate

967 liquidus, partitioning behaviour). To obtain a composition close to the Earth, it is nec-
968 essary to accrete 60 to 80 % of reduced material, and to equilibrate metal and silicate
969 in a magma ocean at an average pressure between 20 and 45 GPa (the average being taken
970 on the full accretion process). The temperature of the core is higher if the magma ocean
971 is maintained throughout the entire accretion, while a transition from a shallow to a deep
972 magma ocean favor lower temperature of the core. The heat content and temperature
973 of the core are controlled by the compressional heating during metallic descent, with neg-
974 ligible effect of diffusion between the diapirs and surrounding mantle, and small effect
975 of the dissipation of gravitational energy. The initial heat content, ranging from 8.92 to
976 $9.55 \cdot 10^{30}$ J, is dependent on the evolution of the metal-silicate segregation.

977 Our models favor relatively 'cold' mixed core, with the more probable range of CMB
978 temperature (after core mixing) between ~ 3950 and 4150 K, depending on the accre-
979 tion style. Loss of heat to the mantle is a negligible phenomena affecting the core tem-
980 perature compared to the compressional heating. Dissipation of gravitational energy may
981 increase strongly the temperature, for example up to 6500 K if 25% of the gravitational
982 energy released during core formation is dissipated in the metal.

983 For most of the accretion scenarios, mixing the core from a stratified state to a ho-
984 mogeneous and isentropic state requires an external source of energy which represent only
985 a few percent of the kinetic energy of an impact (10^{29} J of potential energy change com-
986 pared to 10^{31} to 10^{32} J for the kinetic energy delivered by giant impacts). It is possi-
987 ble in some case that no external energy is needed: in some scenarios at least parts of
988 the core are unstably stratified, which will facilitate the mixing of the core. On the other
989 hand, models where there is dramatic increasing of the depth at the end of accretion yield
990 more stable stratifications, and therefore other sources of energy need to be added to the
991 core to account for mixing the core.

992 Further modeling is necessary to improve the chemical model on the partitioning
993 of chalcophile elements and heat producing elements so as to further constrain the ini-
994 tial thermal conditions.

995 It will in principle be possible to constrain the core composition by using the tem-
996 perature of the core as well as the density. This goal can be achieved by constraining fur-
997 ther the parameters we used (such as the formation of a basal magma ocean, partition-

ing of the heat producing elements into the core, adequate equation of state of liquide
metal), by experimental work or *ab initio* calculation.

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Availability of the data

The code used in this study, as well as a simplified version, can be downloaded on the Zenodo repository following this link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7661374>.

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